

CAUSATION

International Journal of Science

Endoxaban and other NOACs do not protect against stroke

Research article

Ilija Barukčić¹

¹ Internist, Horandstrasse, 26441 Jever, Germany

* **Correspondence:** E-Mail: Barukcic@t-online.de;
Tel: +49-4466-333; Fax: +49-4466-333.

Impressum:

CAUSATION

International Journal Of Science

Chief-Editor / V. i. S. d. P.:

Ilija Barukčić

Hegelitzer Str. 22

DE-26409 Wittmund-Ardorf (Germany)

© Editorial Team: **EDITORIAL TEAM**

🌐 Website: WWW.CAUSATION.EU

✉ E-Mail: editor@causation.eu

☎ Phone: +(49) 4466 - 333

Year: 2024; Volume: 19; Issue: 10; pp. 5–54.

✉ Received: May 14, 2023

✓ Accepted: May 19, 2023

📅 Published: August 6, 2023

📄 Deutsche Nationalbibliothek Frankfurt

🔗 ISSN: 1863-9542

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8219029

🔍 Find in: [Zenodo](#) [Orcid](#) [Academia ...](#)

Abstract

BACKGROUND:

Current data indicate a global stroke incidence of about 258/100,000/year. Despite the many times dramatic consequences for an individual and the human society, stroke is still not preventable for sure. Are direct inhibitors of factor Xa like Apixaban, Edoxaban, Rivaroxaban and other new oral anticoagulants (NOAC) of any benefit for patients in this regard at all?

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The relationship between NOACs and stroke has been re-analysed. New statistical methods were used.

RESULTS:

NOACs do not protect people against stroke, for sure. There is some slight evidence that statins protect people against venous thromboembolism (P Value = 0.00468021).

CONCLUSION:

It appears to be necessary to re-think the unconcerned use of new oral anticoagulants against stroke.

Keywords:

Apixaban; Edoxaban; Rivaroxaban; Stroke; Statins; Venous thromboembolism; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

☉ Reviewer 1: None/Author.

☉ Reviewer 2: None.

☉ Reviewer 3: None.

1. Introduction

Blood clots in the veins, a condition also referred to as venous thromboembolism (VTE), occurs in 1 to 2 individuals per 1000 each year¹ and are a serious medical condition that can cause even death. Venous thromboembolism includes both deep-vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE). In about one third of patients with symptomatic VTE manifest pulmonary embolism (PE), while two thirds manifest deep vein thrombosis (DVT) alone. Within 1 month of diagnosis, death occurs in approximately 6% of DVT cases and 12% of PE.² Major surgery and active cancer are treated as strong provoking risk factors for venous thromboembolism. Nonetheless, most events of VTE are unprovoked. Independent of D-dimer concentrations, ultrasonography, CT or ventilation-perfusion scintigraphy et cetera, the diagnosis of venous thromboembolism is not simple. Studies investigated the relationship between anticoagulants^{3, 4} and stroke⁵ but provided contradictory results.⁶ Drs. J. Marshall and D. A. Shaw with Sir A. Bradford Hill conducted a long-term anticoagulant therapy trial in patients with cerebrovascular disease which started in October, 1957, and progress during the first 20 months to June, 1959.^{7, 8} The study was based on 71 patients treated with anticoagulants and 71 controls. As known, the coumarin anticoagulants act by decreasing hepatic synthesis of four normal Vitamin K-dependent coagulation factors like factor II, factor VII, factor IX and factor X. However, there was no evidence that anticoagulants were reducing either the mortality or the recurrence rate of cerebrovascular accidents. Today, direct new oral anticoagulants (NOAC) like endoxaban and others changed the management strategies of VTE and are changing the management strategies of VTE dramatically even if the routine use of thrombolysis or inferior vena cava (IVC) filters are not recommended.⁹ In patients with venous thromboembolism provoked by a major transient risk factor, anticoagulation is discontinued after completing 3-6 months of initial treatment. However, there are patients whose long-term risk of recurrent venous thromboembolism (active cancer or men with unprovoked venous thromboembolism) outweighs the long-term risk of major bleeding. Usually, these patients are receiving indefinite anticoagulant treatment.¹⁰ Are these drugs of any use?

¹Kollias A, Kyriakoulis KG, Lagou S, Kontopantelis E, Stergiou GS, Syrigos K. Venous thromboembolism in COVID-19: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Vasc Med.* 2021 Aug;26(4):415-425. doi: 10.1177/1358863X21995566. Epub 2021 Apr 4. PMID: 33818197; PMCID: PMC8024143.

²White RH. The epidemiology of venous thromboembolism. *Circulation.* 2003 Jun 17;107(23 Suppl 1):I4-8. doi: 10.1161/01.CIR.0000078468.11849.66. PMID: 12814979.

³FISHER CM. The use of anticoagulants in cerebral thrombosis. *Neurology.* 1958 May;8(5):311-32. doi: 10.1212/wnl.8.5.311. PMID: 13541633.

⁴FISHER CM. Anticoagulant therapy in cerebral thrombosis and cerebral embolism. A national cooperative study, interim report. *Neurology.* 1961 Apr;11(4)Pt 2:119-31. doi: https://doi.org/10.1212/wnl.11.4_part.2.119 PMID: 13699939.

⁵MILLIKAN CH, SIEKERT RG, WHISNANT JP. Anticoagulant therapy in cerebral vascular disease; current status. *J Am Med Assoc.* 1958 Feb 8;166(6):587-92. doi: 10.1001/jama.1958.02990060025006. PMID: 13502031.

⁶The International Stroke Trial (IST): a randomised trial of aspirin, subcutaneous heparin, both, or neither among 19435 patients with acute ischaemic stroke. International Stroke Trial Collaborative Group. *Lancet.* 1997 May 31;349(9065):1569-81. PMID: 9174558.

⁷HILL AB, MARSHALL J, SHAW DA. A controlled clinical trial of long-term anticoagulant therapy in cerebrovascular disease. *Q J Med.* 1960 Oct;29:597-609. PMID: 13714253.

⁸HILL AB, MARSHALL J, SHAW DA. Cerebrovascular disease: trial of long-term anticoagulant therapy. *Br Med J.* 1962 Oct 20;2(5311):1003-6. doi: 10.1136/bmj.2.5311.1003. PMID: 13954494; PMCID: PMC1926325.

⁹Yamashita Y, Morimoto T, Kimura T. Venous thromboembolism: Recent advancement and future perspective. *J Cardiol.* 2022 Jan;79(1):79-89. doi: 10.1016/j.jjcc.2021.08.026. Epub 2021 Sep 10. PMID: 34518074.

¹⁰Khan F, Tritschler T, Kahn SR, Rodger MA. Venous thromboembolism. *Lancet.* 2021 Jul 3;398(10294):64-77. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)32658-1. Epub 2021 May 10. PMID: 33984268.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

As the population ages, stroke might become more and more a major health problem. In the United States, more than 700,000 strokes occur each year and are responsible for more than 165,000 deaths¹¹,¹² while the U.S. population in the year 2004 has been about 292,800,000 inhabitants. The incidence of stroke in the U.S. population (2004) has been about $\left(\frac{700000}{292800000}\right) \times 100 = 0.2390710383\%$ while the global stroke incidence 2016 has been about $\left(\frac{258}{100000}\right) \times 100 = 0.258\%$.¹³ However, the age-adjusted incidence of stroke (Kissela et al., 2012) rapidly increases with age, doubling (Ovbiagele and Nguyen-Huynh, 2011) for each decade after age 55 (Chong and Sacco, 2005).

Table 1. USA. The 2005 age specific incidence of stroke (Kissela et al., 2012)

Age	Stroke incidence per 100.000 per year	per cent per year
0 to 15	6.40	0.0064 %
20 to 44	58	0.058 %
45 to 54	305	0.305 %
55 to 64	524	0.524 %
65 to 74	837	0.837 %
74 to 84	959	0.959 %
85+	1831	1.831 %

In general, often silent strokes fail to come to attention due to the lack clinically stroke-like symptoms. Thus far, silent brain infarcts (Saini et al., 2012) are not really captured by the population incidence of stroke, however, not in a study either. Under these considerations, the incidence of stroke in the population seems to us to be more or less utilisable.

¹¹Ingall T. Stroke—incidence, mortality, morbidity and risk. *J Insur Med.* 2004;36(2):143-52. PMID: 15301227.

¹²BD 2019 Stroke Collaborators. Global, regional, and national burden of stroke and its risk factors, 1990-2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *Lancet Neurol.* 2021 Oct;20(10):795-820. doi: 10.1016/S1474-4422(21)00252-0. Epub 2021 Sep 3. PMID: 34487721; PMCID: PMC8443449.

¹³Béjot Y, Daubail B, Giroud M. Epidemiology of stroke and transient ischemic attacks: Current knowledge and perspectives. *Rev Neurol (Paris).* 2016 Jan;172(1):59-68. doi: 10.1016/j.neurol.2015.07.013. Epub 2015 Dec 21. PMID: 26718592.

2.1.1.1. RE-LY trial, 2011

Vitamin K antagonists such as warfarin are in use to reduce the risk of cardioembolic stroke especially in patients with atrial fibrillation. However, warfarin therapy requires more or less a cost-intensive routine coagulation monitoring. Jeremy S Paikin et al.¹⁴ investigated patients aged 65–74 years and more in the Randomized Evaluation of Long-Term Anticoagulation (RE-LY) trial of 18,113 patients (Paikin et al., 2011) whether dabigatran compared with warfarin, is able to reduce the rate of stroke. The follow-up has been about 2 years. The results are as follows (see table 2).

Table 2. Relationship: Dabigatran etexilate 110 mg bid and Stroke (Study of RE-LY trial, 2011 (Paikin et al., 2011), 2011).

		Stroke		
		YES	NO	
Dabigatran etexilate 110 mg bid	YES	183	5832	6015
	NO	203	5819	6022
		386	11651	12037

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = -0,00932509$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,16568991
p (EXCL) = 0,98479688
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,96957606
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,52590674

P VALUES.
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,16568991
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_t) = 5,56758105
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_t) = 86,75906736
 P Value (EXCL) = **0,01508814**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (183 / 12037) \times 100 = 1,52 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (5832 / 12037) \times 100 = 48,45 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (203 / 12037) \times 100 = 1,69 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (5819 / 12037) \times 100 = 48,34 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (183 / 6015) \times 100 = 3,04 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (5832 / 6015) \times 100 = 96,96 \%$
 $(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (203 / 6022) \times 100 = 3,37 \%$
 $(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (5819 / 6022) \times 100 = 96,63 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (183 / 386) \times 100 = 47,41 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (203 / 386) \times 100 = 52,59 \%$
 $(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (5832 / 11651) \times 100 = 50,06 \%$
 $(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (5819 / 11651) \times 100 = 49,94 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (6015 / 12037) \times 100 = 49,97 \%$
 $(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (6022 / 12037) \times 100 = 50,03 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (386 / 12037) \times 100 = 3,21 \%$
 $(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (11651 / 12037) \times 100 = 96,79 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
 RR (necessary condition) = 0,90252693
 RR (sufficient condition) = 0,94712974
 Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 9,75 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
 Odds ratio (OR) = 0,89946837
 Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,05126174

STUDY DESIGN.
 p(IOU) = 0,46822298
p(IOI) = 0,46764144

¹⁴Paikin JS, Haroun MJ, Eikelboom JW. Dabigatran for stroke prevention in atrial fibrillation: the RE-LY trial. *Expert Rev Cardiovasc Ther.* 2011 Mar;9(3):279-86. doi: 10.1586/erc.11.21. PMID: 21438804.

However, the data provided by Paikin et al. (Paikin et al., 2011) are not really convincing. The age-specific incidence rate of stroke for people aged 65–74 is about 837 per 100000 inhabitants per year (see table 1). A control group of people who are applied only 1 glass of fresh and healthy water (placebo) with a sample size of $n = 6022$ should suffer from $\frac{(837)}{(100000)} \times 2(\text{years}) \times 6022 = 100,81$ events in 2 years. Thus far, we obtain the following fictive placebo group and data (see table 3 and table 1).

Table 3. Relationship: Dabigatran etexilate 110 mg bid and stroke (The RE-LY trial 2011 (Paikin et al., 2011), fictive and fair placebo group).

		Stroke		
		YES	NO	
Dabigatran etexilate 110 mg bid	YES	183	5832	6015
	NO	101	5921	6022
		284	11753	12037

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,04497325$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,99999975
p (EXCL) = 0,98479688
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,96957606
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,35563380

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,99999975
 χ^2 (EXCL—A_i) = 5,56758105
 χ^2 (EXCL—B_i) = 117,91901408
P Value (EXCL) = **0,01508814**

PROPORTIONS.

(a/N) × 100 = (183 / 12037) × 100 = 1,52 %
(b/N) × 100 = (5832 / 12037) × 100 = 48,45 %
(c/N) × 100 = (101 / 12037) × 100 = 0,84 %
(d/N) × 100 = (5921 / 12037) × 100 = 49,19 %
(a/A) × 100 = (183 / 6015) × 100 = 3,04 %
(b/A) × 100 = (5832 / 6015) × 100 = 96,96 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (101 / 6022) × 100 = 1,68 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (5921 / 6022) × 100 = 98,32 %
(a/B) × 100 = (183 / 284) × 100 = 64,44 %
(c/B) × 100 = (101 / 284) × 100 = 35,56 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (5832 / 11753) × 100 = 49,62 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (5921 / 11753) × 100 = 50,38 %
(A/N) × 100 = (6015 / 12037) × 100 = 49,97 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (6022 / 12037) × 100 = 50,03 %
(B/N) × 100 = (284 / 12037) × 100 = 2,36 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (11753 / 12037) × 100 = 97,64 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 1,81398978
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,29856583
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = -81,40 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 1,83953164
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,28948228

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = 0,47669685
p(IOI) = 0,47611531

The RE-LY trial, 2011 (Paikin et al., 2011) based on a fair placebo group did not provide any significant evidence of an exclusion relationship between dabigatran etexilate 110 mg bid and stroke ($k = +0,04497325$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,99999975) with p (EXCL) = 0,984796876 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,01508814). Quite the contrary. There is some evidence that the intake of dabigatran etexilate 110 mg bid harms people (RR (necessary condition) = +1,81398978; RR (sufficient condition) = +1,29856583).

2.1.2. ARISTOTLE study, 2011

Vitamin K antagonists are assumed to be highly effective in preventing stroke in patients with atrial fibrillation, but have several limitations. The ARISTOTLE study¹⁵ investigated the non-inferiority of Apixaban (Granger et al., 2011), a novel oral direct factor Xa inhibitor, against warfarin. Follow-up was about 2 years, age 63-76. The results are as follows (see table 4).

Table 4. Relationship: apixaban and stroke (Aristotle trial (Granger et al., 2011)).

		stroke		
		YES	NO	
apixaban	YES	202	8918	9120
	NO	253	8828	9081
		455	17746	18201

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship k = -0,01829107
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00771581
p (EXCL) = 0,98890171
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,97785088
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,55604396

P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00771581
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 4,47412281
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 89,67912088
P Value (EXCL) = **0,01103693**

PROPORTIONS.
(a/N) × 100 = (202 / 18201) × 100 = 1,11 %
(b/N) × 100 = (8918 / 18201) × 100 = 49,00 %
(c/N) × 100 = (253 / 18201) × 100 = 1,39 %
(d/N) × 100 = (8828 / 18201) × 100 = 48,50 %
(a/A) × 100 = (202 / 9120) × 100 = 2,21 %
(b/A) × 100 = (8918 / 9120) × 100 = 97,79 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (253 / 9081) × 100 = 2,79 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (8828 / 9081) × 100 = 97,21 %
(a/B) × 100 = (202 / 455) × 100 = 44,40 %
(c/B) × 100 = (253 / 455) × 100 = 55,60 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (8918 / 17746) × 100 = 50,25 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (8828 / 17746) × 100 = 49,75 %
(A/N) × 100 = (9120 / 18201) × 100 = 50,11 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (9081 / 18201) × 100 = 49,89 %
(B/N) × 100 = (455 / 18201) × 100 = 2,50 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (17746 / 18201) × 100 = 97,50 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,79500468
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,88343171
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 20,50 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,79036137
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,11398641

STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU)= 0,47393000
p(IOI)= 0,47607274

¹⁵Granger CB, Alexander JH, McMurray JJ, Lopes RD, Hylek EM, Hanna M, Al-Khalidi HR, Ansell J, Atar D, Avezum A, Bahit MC, Diaz R, Easton JD, Ezekowitz JA, Flaker G, Garcia D, Gerald M, Gersh BJ, Golitsyn S, Goto S, Hermosillo AG, Hohnloser SH, Horowitz J, Mohan P, Jansky P, Lewis BS, Lopez-Sendon JL, Pais P, Parkhomenko A, Verheugt FW, Zhu J, Wallentin L; ARISTOTLE Committees and Investigators. Apixaban versus warfarin in patients with atrial fibrillation. N Engl J Med. 2011 Sep 15;365(11):981-92. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1107039. Epub 2011 Aug 27. PMID: 21870978.

However, the Aristotle trial (Granger et al., 2011) did not provide any significant evidence of an exclusion relationship between apixaban and stroke. The age 63-76 specific incidence of stroke is less than 959 per 100000 per year (see table 1). A control group of people who are applied only 1 glass of fresh and healthy water (placebo) with a sample size of $n = 9081$ should suffer in 2 years from $\frac{(959)}{(100000)} \times 2 \times 9081 \equiv 174,1$ events. The data and the results are presented by table 5.

Table 5. Relationship: apixaban and stroke (Aristotle trial (Granger et al., 2011), fictive and fair placebo group).

		stroke		
		YES	NO	
apixaban	YES	202	8918	9120
	NO	174	8907	9081
		376	17825	18201

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = 0,01050439$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,92917489
p (EXCL) = 0,98890171
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,97785088
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,46276596

P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,92917489
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 4,47412281
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 108,52127660
P Value (EXCL) = **0,01103693**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (202 / 18201) \times 100 = 1,11 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (8918 / 18201) \times 100 = 49,00 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (174 / 18201) \times 100 = 0,96 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (8907 / 18201) \times 100 = 48,94 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (202 / 9120) \times 100 = 2,21 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (8918 / 9120) \times 100 = 97,79 \%$
 $(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (174 / 9081) \times 100 = 1,92 \%$
 $(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (8907 / 9081) \times 100 = 98,08 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (202 / 376) \times 100 = 53,72 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (174 / 376) \times 100 = 46,28 \%$
 $(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (8918 / 17825) \times 100 = 50,03 \%$
 $(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (8907 / 17825) \times 100 = 49,97 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (9120 / 18201) \times 100 = 50,11 \%$
 $(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (9081 / 18201) \times 100 = 49,89 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (376 / 18201) \times 100 = 2,07 \%$
 $(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (17825 / 18201) \times 100 = 97,93 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 1,15595508
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,07380543
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = -15,60 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 1,15948759
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,07217070

STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU) = 0,47827042
p(IOI) = 0,48041316

The Aristotle trial (Granger et al., 2011) failed to provide significant evidence of an exclusion relationship between apixaban and stroke ($k = +0,01050439$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,92917489) with $p(\text{EXCL}) = 0,988901709$ (P Value (EXCL) = 0,01103693).

2.1.3. ROCKET AF trial, 2011

The Rivaroxaban Versus Warfarin In Non-valvular Atrial Fibrillation (ROCKET AF) double-blinded, randomized control trial (Patel et al., 2011) investigated 14,264 patients with non-valvular AF of various ages randomized to warfarin or rivaroxaban¹⁶ and looked for stroke. During treatment in the intention-to-treat population, patients in the warfarin group (N= 7004) suffered 241 events, or 2.2% per year. In the primary analysis, stroke or pulmonary embolism occurred in 188/6958 patients in the rivaroxaban group (1.7% per year). The median duration of treatment exposure was about 590 days, age 65-78. The follow-up has been about 1,6 years while the results are as follows (see table 6).

Table 6. Relationship: rivaroxaban and stroke (Study of ROCKET AF trial (Patel et al., 2011)).

		stroke		
		YES	NO	
rivaroxaban	YES	188	6770	6958
	NO	241	6763	7004
		429	13533	13962

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = -0,02140984$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00650722
 p (EXCL) = 0,98653488
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) > 0,97298074$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) > 0,56177156$

P VALUES.
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00650722
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_r) = 5,07962058
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_r) = 82,38694639
 P Value (EXCL) = 0,01337487

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (188 / 13962) \times 100 = 1,35 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (6770 / 13962) \times 100 = 48,49 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (241 / 13962) \times 100 = 1,73 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (6763 / 13962) \times 100 = 48,44 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (188 / 6958) \times 100 = 2,70 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (6770 / 6958) \times 100 = 97,30 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (241 / 7004) \times 100 = 3,44 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (6763 / 7004) \times 100 = 96,56 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (188 / 429) \times 100 = 43,82 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (241 / 429) \times 100 = 56,18 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (6770 / 13533) \times 100 = 50,03 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (6763 / 13533) \times 100 = 49,97 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (6958 / 13962) \times 100 = 49,84 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (7004 / 13962) \times 100 = 50,16 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (429 / 13962) \times 100 = 3,07 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (13533 / 13962) \times 100 = 96,93 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
 RR (necessary condition) = 0,78524019
 RR (sufficient condition) = 0,87600376
 Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 21,48 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
 Odds ratio (OR) = 0,77927640
 Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,12064595

STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,47092107$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,46762641$

¹⁶Patel MR, Mahaffey KW, Garg J, Pan G, Singer DE, Hacke W, Breithardt G, Halperin JL, Hankey GJ, Piccini JP, Becker RC, Nessel CC, Paolini JF, Berkowitz SD, Fox KA, Califf RM; ROCKET AF Investigators. Rivaroxaban versus warfarin in nonvalvular atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med.* 2011 Sep 8;365(10):883-91. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1009638. Epub 2011 Aug 10. PMID: 21830957.

Formally, rivaroxaban (Patel et al., 2011) provided some slight evidence of an exclusion relationship between an intake of rivaroxaban and stroke ($k = -0,02140984$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00650722) with p (EXCL) = 0,98653488 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,01337487). However, to what extent can we rely on the study design and the data published. The 65-78 age-specific incidence of stroke is less than 959 per 100000 per year (see table 1). A control group of people who are applied only 1 glass of fresh and healthy water (placebo) with a sample size of $n = 7004$ should suffer from $\frac{(959)}{(100000)} \times 1,6(\text{years}) \times 7004 \equiv 108,6$ events. The data and the results are presented by table 7.

Table 7. Relationship: rivaroxaban and stroke (Study of ROCKET AF trial (Patel et al., 2011), fictive and fair placebo group).

		stroke		
		YES	NO	
rivaroxaban	YES	188	6770	6958
	NO	109	6895	7004
		297	13665	13962

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,03970020$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,99999911
 p (EXCL) = 0,98653488
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) > 0,97298074$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) > 0,36700337$

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,99999911
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 5,07962058
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 119,00336700
P Value (EXCL) = **0,01337487**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (188 / 13962) \times 100 = 1,35 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (6770 / 13962) \times 100 = 48,49 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (109 / 13962) \times 100 = 0,78 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (6895 / 13962) \times 100 = 49,38 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (188 / 6958) \times 100 = 2,70 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (6770 / 6958) \times 100 = 97,30 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (109 / 7004) \times 100 = 1,56 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (6895 / 7004) \times 100 = 98,44 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (188 / 297) \times 100 = 63,30 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (109 / 297) \times 100 = 36,70 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (6770 / 13665) \times 100 = 49,54 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (6895 / 13665) \times 100 = 50,46 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (6958 / 13962) \times 100 = 49,84 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (7004 / 13962) \times 100 = 50,16 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (297 / 13962) \times 100 = 2,13 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (13665 / 13962) \times 100 = 97,87 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 1,73617327
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,27768080
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = -73,62 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 1,75661648
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,27017807

STUDY DESIGN.

$p(\text{IOU}) = 0,48037530$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,47708065$

Based on the data published, the ROCKET AF trial (Patel et al., 2011) did not provide any evidence of an exclusion relationship between rivaroxaban and stroke ($k = +0,03970020$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,99999911) with p (EXCL) = 0,98653488 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,01337487).

2.1.4. The ENGAGE AF-TIMI 48 Trial, 2013

Giugliano et al. ¹⁷ conducted a randomized, double-blind, double-dummy trial comparing two once-daily regimens of edoxaban with warfarin in order to evaluate clinical outcomes with the use of the direct Xa inhibitor edoxaban versus warfarin (ENGAGE AF-TIMI 48 trial). In the high-dose Edoxaban (N =7035) group, stroke occurred in about 281 cases or $\left(\frac{281}{7035}\right) \times 100 = 3.994314144\%$ during a period of about 3 years (median follow-up, 2.8 years), age 64-78. In other words, the average incidence of stroke in the high-dose Edoxaban (N =7035) group has been about $\left(\frac{\frac{281}{7035}}{3}\right) \times 100 = 1.331438048\%$ per year. The age-specific incidence of stroke in a population aged 64-78 which takes only 1 glass of healthy water daily is less than 1.0%. per year (see table 1). This simple circumstance makes it impossible for us to believe that Endoxaban is protective against stroke at all. Furthermore, the study design of the study of Giugliano et al. with $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,45746571$ has been very unfair (see table 8). The exclusion relationship between edoxaban 60 mg and stroke with $p(\text{EXCL}) = 0,98002985$ (P Value (EXCL) = 0,01977207; N = 14071) is not convincing.

Table 8. Relationship: edoxaban and stroke (Study of Giugliano et al., 2013).

		Stroke		
		YES	NO	
Endoxaban	YES	281	6754	7035
	NO	317	6719	7036
		598	13473	14071

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = -0,01266796$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,07199244
 $p(\text{EXCL}) = 0,98002985$
 $p(\text{EXCL}) \text{ approx.} = 1-(a/A) > 0,96005686$
 $p(\text{EXCL}) \text{ approx.} = 1-(a/B) > 0,53010033$
P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,07199244
 $\chi^2(\text{EXCL} - A_i) = 11,22402274$
 $\chi^2(\text{EXCL} - B_i) = 132,04180602$
P Value (EXCL) = **0,01977207**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (281 / 14071) \times 100 = 2,00 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (6754 / 14071) \times 100 = 48,00 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (317 / 14071) \times 100 = 2,25 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (6719 / 14071) \times 100 = 47,75 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (281 / 7035) \times 100 = 3,99 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (6754 / 7035) \times 100 = 96,01 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (317 / 7036) \times 100 = 4,51 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (6719 / 7036) \times 100 = 95,49 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (281 / 598) \times 100 = 46,99 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (317 / 598) \times 100 = 53,01 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (6754 / 13473) \times 100 = 50,13 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (6719 / 13473) \times 100 = 49,87 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (7035 / 14071) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (7036 / 14071) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (598 / 14071) \times 100 = 4,25 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (13473 / 14071) \times 100 = 95,75 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,88656133
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,93736426

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,88184172
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,06013387

STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,45753678$
 $p(\text{IO}) = 0,45746571$

¹⁷Giugliano RP, Ruff CT, Braunwald E, Murphy SA, Wiviott SD, Halperin JL, Waldo AL, Ezekowitz MD, Weitz JI, Špinar J, Ruzyllo W, Ruda M, Koretsune Y, Betcher J, Shi M, Grip LT, Patel SP, Patel I, Hanyok JJ, Mercuri M, Antman EM; ENGAGE AF-TIMI 48 Investigators. Edoxaban versus warfarin in patients with atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med.* 2013 Nov 28;369(22):2093-104. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1310907. Epub 2013 Nov 19. PMID: 24251359.

Unfortunately, the data of the study of Giugliano et al. do not provide convincing evidence that endoxaban is reliably effective against stroke. Quite the opposite. Is the intake of endoxaban rather harmful in this regard.

In general, **the strategy of comparing the Bad and the Ugly** can be associated with systemic bias. While comparing something identified for sure as Bad with something known as Ugly, the Bad may appear to us as being quite good and as the lesser of two evils. Even if such a worthless comparison may be suitable for misleading and deceiving the reader, the same act of comparison does not change the fact that we are dealing with two which are Bad, even if the one is less Bad than the other. Something which is Bad, is Bad, and only a mere act of comparison cannot change such a fundamental property of an entity or magic away the badness. The comparison of something Ugly or Terrible with something Bad can lead us astray and might induce massive epistemological distortions. The question may be asked whether it is more appropriate to compare something Bad with something Good or at least neutral, or to compare something Ugly or Terrible with something Good or at least neutral.

2.1.5. The ENGAGE AF-TIMI 48 Trial, 2013 (Fictive data)

Epidemiological measures like prevalence and incidence are the foundation to conduct scientific research or to monitor diseases et cetera. In general, prevalence is defined as the proportion of the population with a certain condition during a period of time (period prevalence) or even at a specific point in time (point prevalence).¹⁸ Incidence is defined as the frequency of new occurrences of a medical disorders or a certain event in the studied population during a period of time (period incidence) or even at a specific point in time (point incidence).¹⁹ In the case that endoxaban 60 mg is effective against stroke, the incidence in the verum group taking endoxaban 60 mg should be lower than in the placebo group drinking only 1 glass of healthy water. The fictitious data presented below are based on the following considerations. In the high-dose edoxaban 60 mg group (N =7035) group, stroke occurred in about 281 cases. The age-specific 3-year incidence rate of stroke in a population aged 64-78 is about $3 \times \left(\frac{837}{100.000}\right) \times 100 = 3 \times 0.837 = 2.511\%$ (see also table 1). A control group of people who are applied only 1 glass of fresh and healthy water (placebo) with a sample size of n = 7036 should suffer from $\left(\frac{2.511}{100}\right) \times 7036 = 177$ new strokes in about 3 years. Under these assumptions, we obtain the following, fictitious data.

Table 9. Relationship: endoxaban and stroke (Study of Giugliano et al., 2013, fictive and fair placebo group).

		Stroke		
		YES	NO	
Endoxaban	YES	281	6754	7035
	NO	177	6859	7036
		458	13613	14071

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.	
Causal relationship k =	0,04166387
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) =	0,99999973
p (EXCL) =	0,98002985
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) >	0,96005686
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) >	0,38646288
P VALUES.	
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) =	0,99999973
Z ² (EXCL— A) =	11,22402274
Z ² (EXCL— B) =	172,40393013
P Value (EXCL) =	0,01977207
PROPORTIONS.	
(a/N) × 100 = (281 / 14071) × 100 =	2,00 %
(b/N) × 100 = (6754 / 14071) × 100 =	48,00 %
(c/N) × 100 = (177 / 14071) × 100 =	1,26 %
(d/N) × 100 = (6859 / 14071) × 100 =	48,75 %
(a/A) × 100 = (281 / 7035) × 100 =	3,99 %
(b/A) × 100 = (6754 / 7035) × 100 =	96,01 %
(c/not A) × 100 = (177 / 7036) × 100 =	2,52 %
(d/not A) × 100 = (6859 / 7036) × 100 =	97,48 %
(a/B) × 100 = (281 / 458) × 100 =	61,35 %
(c/B) × 100 = (177 / 458) × 100 =	38,65 %
(b/not B) × 100 = (6754 / 13613) × 100 =	49,61 %
(d/not B) × 100 = (6859 / 13613) × 100 =	50,39 %
(A/N) × 100 = (7035 / 14071) × 100 =	50,00 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (7036 / 14071) × 100 =	50,00 %
(B/N) × 100 = (458 / 14071) × 100 =	3,25 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (13613 / 14071) × 100 =	96,75 %
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.	
RELATIVE RISK (RR).	
RR (necessary condition) =	1,58779629
RR (sufficient condition) =	1,23661249
Relative risk reduction (RRR) =	-58,78 %
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.	
Odds ratio (OR) =	1,61225154
Index of relationship (IOR) =	0,22716145
STUDY DESIGN.	
p(OU) =	0,46748632
p(OI) =	0,46741525

The incidence of stroke in the placebo group is given as $(c/notA) \times 100 = (55/7036) \times 100 = 0,78\%$. As shown by the fictitious data, endoxaban does not protect against stroke in any way.

¹⁸Tenny S, Hoffman MR. Prevalence. 2022 May 24. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. PMID: 28613617.

¹⁹Spronk I, Korevaar JC, Poos R, Davids R, Hilderink H, Schellevis FG, Verheij RA, Nielen MMJ. Calculating incidence rates and prevalence proportions: not as simple as it seems. BMC Public Health. 2019 May 6;19(1):512. doi: 10.1186/s12889-019-6820-3. PMID: 31060532; PMCID: PMC6501456.

2.1.6. The ENGAGE AF-TIMI 48 Trial, 2013: Endoxan and systemic embolic events

The relationship between Low-Dose Endoxaban (30 mg) and systemic embolic events is presented by table 10.

Table 10. Relationship: Low-Dose Endoxaban (30 mg) and Systemic embolic events (Study of Giugliano et al., 2013).

		Systemic embolic events		
		YES	NO	
Low-Dose Endoxaban (30 mg)	YES	29	7005	7034
	NO	23	7013	7036
		52	14018	14070

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,00703625$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,83483031
p (EXCL) = 0,99793888
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,99587717
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,44230769

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,83483031
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_t) = 0,11956213
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_t) = 16,17307692
 P Value (EXCL) = **0,00205900**

PROPORTIONS.

(a/N) × 100 = (29 / 14070) × 100 = 0,21 %
 (b/N) × 100 = (7005 / 14070) × 100 = 49,79 %
 (c/N) × 100 = (23 / 14070) × 100 = 0,16 %
 (d/N) × 100 = (7013 / 14070) × 100 = 49,84 %
 (a/A) × 100 = (29 / 7034) × 100 = 0,41 %
 (b/A) × 100 = (7005 / 7034) × 100 = 99,59 %
 (c/ not A) × 100 = (23 / 7036) × 100 = 0,33 %
 (d/ not A) × 100 = (7013 / 7036) × 100 = 99,67 %
 (a/B) × 100 = (29 / 52) × 100 = 55,77 %
 (c/B) × 100 = (23 / 52) × 100 = 44,23 %
 (b/ not B) × 100 = (7005 / 14018) × 100 = 49,97 %
 (d/ not B) × 100 = (7013 / 14018) × 100 = 50,03 %
 (A/N) × 100 = (7034 / 14070) × 100 = 49,99 %
 (not A/N) × 100 = (7036 / 14070) × 100 = 50,01 %
 (B/N) × 100 = (52 / 14070) × 100 = 0,37 %
 (not B/N) × 100 = (14018 / 14070) × 100 = 99,63 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 1,26122807
 RR (sufficient condition) = 1,11602152

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 1,26230953
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,11554319

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = 0,49637527
p(IOI) = 0,49623312

However, Giugliano et al. were not able to provide convincing evidence of an exclusion relationship between Low-Dose Endoxaban (30 mg) and systemic embolic event ($k = +0,00703625$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,83483031) with p (EXCL) = 0,997938877 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00205900). A positive causal relationship excludes the possibility of a significant exclusion relationship. Furthermore, the study design (p (IOI) = 0,49623312) has been very unfair (Barukčić, 2019a).

2.1.7. The ENGAGE AF-TIMI 48 Trial, 2013: Warfarin and systemic embolic events

The ENGAGE AF-TIMI 48 Trial provided data about the relationship between Warfarin and systemic embolic events (see table 11).

Table 11. Relationship: Warfarin and systemic embolic event (Study of Giugliano et al. , 2013).

		Systemic embolic event		
		YES	NO	
Warfarin	YES	23	7013	7036
	NO	29	7005	7034
		52	14018	14070

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = -0,00703625$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,24349999
p (EXCL) = 0,99836532
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,99673110
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,55769231

P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,24349999
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 0,07518476
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 10,17307692
P Value (EXCL) = **0,00163335**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (23 / 14070) \times 100 = 0,16 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (7013 / 14070) \times 100 = 49,84 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (29 / 14070) \times 100 = 0,21 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (7005 / 14070) \times 100 = 49,79 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (23 / 7036) \times 100 = 0,33 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (7013 / 7036) \times 100 = 99,67 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (29 / 7034) \times 100 = 0,41 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (7005 / 7034) \times 100 = 99,59 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (23 / 52) \times 100 = 44,23 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (29 / 52) \times 100 = 55,77 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (7013 / 14018) \times 100 = 50,03 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (7005 / 14018) \times 100 = 49,97 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (7036 / 14070) \times 100 = 50,01 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (7034 / 14070) \times 100 = 49,99 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (52 / 14070) \times 100 = 0,37 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (14018 / 14070) \times 100 = 99,63 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,79287801
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,88411083

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,79219872
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,11551034

STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU)= 0,49623312
p(IOI)= 0,49637527

These data of Giugliano et al. support only very cautiously an exclusion relationship between Warfarin and Systemic embolic events ($k = -0,00703625$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,24349999) with p (EXCL) = 0,998365316 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00163335). However, the study design (p (IOI) = 0,49637527) has been very unfair (Barukčić, 2019a).

2.1.8. The ENGAGE AF-TIMI 48 Trial, 2013: Endoxaban and death due to any cause

Table 12. Relationship: Low-Dose Endoxaban (30 mg) and Death (Any cause) (Study of Giugliano et al., 2013).

	Death (Any cause)		
		YES	NO
Low-Dose Endoxaban (30 mg)	YES	737	6297
	NO	839	7721
		1576	14018
			15594

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,01116457$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,92223100
 p (EXCL) = 0,95273823
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) > 0,89522320$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) > 0,53236041$

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,92223100
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 77,22050043
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 344,65038071
P Value (EXCL) = **0,04616232**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (737 / 15594) \times 100 = 4,73 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (6297 / 15594) \times 100 = 40,38 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (839 / 15594) \times 100 = 5,38 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (7721 / 15594) \times 100 = 49,51 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (737 / 7034) \times 100 = 10,48 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (6297 / 7034) \times 100 = 89,52 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (839 / 8560) \times 100 = 9,80 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (7721 / 8560) \times 100 = 90,20 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (737 / 1576) \times 100 = 46,76 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (839 / 1576) \times 100 = 53,24 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (6297 / 14018) \times 100 = 44,92 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (7721 / 14018) \times 100 = 55,08 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (7034 / 15594) \times 100 = 45,11 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (8560 / 15594) \times 100 = 54,89 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (1576 / 15594) \times 100 = 10,11 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (14018 / 15594) \times 100 = 89,89 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 1,06899809
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,04103094

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 1,07707361
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,03673185

STUDY DESIGN.

$p(\text{IOU}) = 0,44786456$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,35000641$

Giugliano et al. did not provide any evidence of an exclusion relationship between Low-Dose Endoxaban (30 mg) and Death (due to any cause) ($k = +0,01116457$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,92223100) with p (EXCL) = 0,952738233 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,04616232). A p (EXCL) = 0,952738233 based on a sample size of $N = 15594$ is far beyond any possibility of being accepted. Additionally, the study design ($p(\text{IOI}) = 0,35000641$) has been very unfair (Barukčić, 2019a). The median follow-up of this randomized, double-blind, double-dummy trial comparing edoxaban with warfarin was about 2.8 years with an interquartile age range between 64 and 78 years. However, and as an example, the U.S. death rate increased by 5.3% from 835.4 deaths per 100,000 standard population

in 2020 or $\left(\frac{835.4}{100,000}\right) \times 100 = 0.8354\%$ to 879.7 deaths per 100,000 standard population in 2021. ²⁰ The U. S. age-adjusted death rate for 64 years old until 74 years old has been 2072.3 deaths per 100,000 standard population in 2020 or $\left(\frac{2072.3}{100,000}\right) \times 100 = 2.0723\%$. ²¹ In the following, we compare the data under conditions of fair study design while the age adjusted death rate of the US population from the year 2020 has been used. It is $\left(\frac{c=6297}{X}\right) = 0.020723$. The placebo controlled group for about 3 years (X) is given as $X = \left(\frac{6297}{3 \times 0.020723}\right) = 101288.4235$. The following table illustrates these data (see table 13).

Table 13. Relationship: Low-Dose Endoxaban (30 mg) and Death (Any cause) (Study of Giugliano et al. (Fair study design), 2013).

	Death (Any cause)			
	YES	NO		
Low-Dose Endoxaban (30 mg)	YES	737	6297	7034
	NO	6297	94991	101288
		7034	101288	108322

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship k = + 0.04260754

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 1,00000000

p (EXCL) = 0,99319621

p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,89522320

p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,89522320

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 1,00000000

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 77,22050043

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 77,22050043

P Value (EXCL) = **0,00678070**

PROPORTIONS.

(a/N) × 100 = (737 / 108322) × 100 = 0,68 %

(b/N) × 100 = (6297 / 108322) × 100 = 5,81 %

(c/N) × 100 = (6297 / 108322) × 100 = 5,81 %

(d/N) × 100 = (94991 / 108322) × 100 = 87,69 %

(a/A) × 100 = (737 / 7034) × 100 = 10,48 %

(b/A) × 100 = (6297 / 7034) × 100 = 89,52 %

(c/ not A) × 100 = (6297 / 101288) × 100 = 6,22 %

(d/ not A) × 100 = (94991 / 101288) × 100 = 93,78 %

(a/B) × 100 = (737 / 7034) × 100 = 10,48 %

(c/B) × 100 = (6297 / 7034) × 100 = 89,52 %

(b/ not B) × 100 = (6297 / 101288) × 100 = 6,22 %

(d/ not B) × 100 = (94991 / 101288) × 100 = 93,78 %

(A/N) × 100 = (7034 / 108322) × 100 = 6,49 %

(not A/N) × 100 = (101288 / 108322) × 100 = 93,51 %

(B/N) × 100 = (7034 / 108322) × 100 = 6,49 %

(not B/N) × 100 = (101288 / 108322) × 100 = 93,51 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 1,68534736

RR (sufficient condition) = 1,68534736

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 1,76556032

Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,61353886

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,87012795

p(IOI)= 0,00000000

²⁰Jiaquan Xu, M.D., Sherry L. Murphy, B.S., Kenneth D. Kochanek, M.A., and Elizabeth Arias, Ph.D. Mortality in the United States, 2021. National Center for Health Statistics.

²¹Jiaquan Xu, M.D., Sherry L. Murphy, B.S., Kenneth D. Kochanek, M.A., and Elizabeth Arias, Ph.D. Mortality in the United States, 2021. National Center for Health Statistics.

In the verum group (Low-Dose Endoxaban) 10 % of the population investigated died in about 3 years or $(a/A) \times 100 = (737/7034) \times 100 = 10,48\%$. The fictive study before is based on a placebo group (see table 12) which has been given a glass of healthy and fresh water once a day. In about 3 years 6,22 % of this population investigated should have died or every year about 2,0723%. Under conditions of fair study design, we expect $b = 6297 = c = 6297$ deaths in 3 years in the placebo group, which should equal in about $(b/notB) \times 100 = 6,22\%$. This leads to a necessary sample size of the placebo group of about 101288 participants. This logically founded but fictive data have been re-analysed. Giugliano et al. did not provide any evidence, that endoxaban is of any use for the people, quite the contrary. These fictive data analysed provide a frightening indication that low dose endoxaban has causally contributed to the death of people of the populations investigated ($k = +0,04260754$; RR (necessary condition) = $+1,68534736$; RR (sufficient condition) = $+1,68534736$; Odds ratio (OR) = $+1,76556032$) et cetera. It is reasonable to assume that other new oral anticoagulants (NOAK) like Apixaban²², Rivaroxaban²³, Dabigatran²⁴ et cetera will not provide significantly better or even completely different results. For this reason, these anticoagulants were not subjected to a more detailed investigation in this context. The principle question arises whether the continued use of endoxaban, a direct oral factor Xa inhibitor, or of other direct anticoagulants is of any use for the people, and whether there is or whether there can be a substitute to these anticoagulants under certain circumstances.

²²Granger CB, Alexander JH, McMurray JJ, Lopes RD, Hylek EM, Hanna M, Al-Khalidi HR, Ansell J, Atar D, Avezum A, Bahit MC, Diaz R, Easton JD, Ezekowitz JA, Flaker G, Garcia D, Geraldles M, Gersh BJ, Golitsyn S, Goto S, Hermosillo AG, Hohnloser SH, Horowitz J, Mohan P, Jansky P, Lewis BS, Lopez-Sendon JL, Pais P, Parkhomenko A, Verheugt FW, Zhu J, Wallentin L; ARISTOTLE Committees and Investigators. Apixaban versus warfarin in patients with atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med.* 2011 Sep 15;365(11):981-92. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1107039. Epub 2011 Aug 27. PMID: 21870978.

²³Patel MR, Mahaffey KW, Garg J, Pan G, Singer DE, Hacke W, Breithardt G, Halperin JL, Hankey GJ, Piccini JP, Becker RC, Nessel CC, Paolini JF, Berkowitz SD, Fox KA, Califf RM; ROCKET AF Investigators. Rivaroxaban versus warfarin in nonvalvular atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med.* 2011 Sep 8;365(10):883-91. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1009638. Epub 2011 Aug 10. PMID: 21830957.

²⁴Yaghi S, Shu L, Bakradze E, Salehi Omran S, Giles JA, Amar JY, Henninger N, Elnazeir M, Liberman AL, Moncrieffe K, Lu J, Sharma R, Cheng Y, Zubair AS, Simpkins AN, Li GT, Kung JC, Perez D, Heldner M, Scutelnic A, Seiffge D, Siepen B, Rothstein A, Khazaal O, Do D, Kasab SA, Rahman LA, Mistry EA, Kerrigan D, Lafever H, Nguyen TN, Klein P, Aparicio H, Frontera J, Kuohn L, Agarwal S, Stretz C, Kala N, El Jamal S, Chang A, Cutting S, Xiao H, de Havenon A, Muddasani V, Wu T, Wilson D, Nouh A, Asad SD, Qureshi A, Moore J, Khatri P, Aziz Y, Casteigne B, Khan M, Cheng Y, Mac Grory B, Weiss M, Ryan D, Vedovati MC, Paciaroni M, Siegler JE, Kamen S, Yu S, Leon Guerrero CR, Atallah E, De Marchis GM, Brehm A, Dittrich T, Psychogios M, Alvarado-Dyer R, Kass-Hout T, Prabhakaran S, Honda T, Liebeskind DS, Furie K. Direct Oral Anticoagulants Versus Warfarin in the Treatment of Cerebral Venous Thrombosis (ACTION-CVT): A Multicenter International Study. *Stroke.* 2022 Mar;53(3):728-738. doi: 10.1161/STROKEAHA.121.037541. Epub 2022 Feb 10. PMID: 35143325.

2.1.9. Statins and venous thromboembolism

Several studies ²⁵, ²⁶, ²⁷, ²⁸, ²⁹, ³⁰, ³¹, ³², ³³, ³⁴, ³⁵, ³⁶ including ³⁷, ³⁸, ³⁹, ⁴⁰ provided evidence of a link between statins and reduced risk of deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE), i. e. venous thromboembolism (VTE). ⁴¹

²⁵Schmidt M, Cannegieter SC, Johannesdottir SA, Dekkers OM, Horváth-Puhó E, Sørensen HT. Statin use and venous thromboembolism recurrence: a combined nationwide cohort and nested case-control study. *J Thromb Haemost.* 2014 Aug;12(8):1207-15. doi: 10.1111/jth.12604. Epub 2014 Jun 19. PMID: 24818818.

²⁶Wells PS, Gebel M, Prins MH, Davidson BL, Lensing AW. Influence of statin use on the incidence of recurrent venous thromboembolism and major bleeding in patients receiving rivaroxaban or standard anticoagulant therapy. *Thromb J.* 2014 Nov 26;12:26. doi: 10.1186/1477-9560-12-26. PMID: 25698905; PMCID: PMC4334416.

²⁷Rodríguez AL, Wojcik BM, Wroblewski SK, Myers DD Jr, Wakefield TW, Diaz JA. Statins, inflammation and deep vein thrombosis: a systematic review. *J Thromb Thrombolysis.* 2012 May;33(4):371-82. doi: 10.1007/s11239-012-0687-9. PMID: 22278047; PMCID: PMC3338886.

²⁸Rahimi K, Bhala N, Kamphuisen P, Emberson J, Biere-Rafi S, Krane V, Robertson M, Wikstrand J, McMurray J. Effect of statins on venous thromboembolic events: a meta-analysis of published and unpublished evidence from randomised controlled trials. *PLoS Med.* 2012;9(9):e1001310. doi: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1001310. Epub 2012 Sep 18. PMID: 23028261; PMCID: PMC3445446.

²⁹Rabinowich L, Steinvil A, Leshem-Rubinow E, Berliner S, Zeltser D, Rogowski O, Shalev V, Raz R, Chodick G. Adherence to statins is associated with reduced incidence of idiopathic venous thromboembolism: real-life data from a large healthcare maintenance organisation. *Heart.* 2012 Dec;98(24):1817-21. doi: 10.1136/heartjnl-2012-302906. Epub 2012 Oct 4. PMID: 23038788.

³⁰Glynn RJ, Danielson E, Fonseca FA, Genest J, Gotto AM Jr, Kastelein JJ, Koenig W, Libby P, Lorenzatti AJ, MacFadyen JG, Nordestgaard BG, Shepherd J, Willerson JT, Ridker PM. A randomized trial of rosuvastatin in the prevention of venous thromboembolism. *N Engl J Med.* 2009 Apr 30;360(18):1851-61. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa0900241. Epub 2009 Mar 29. PMID: 19329822; PMCID: PMC2710995.

³¹Lassila R, Jula A, Pitkaniemi J, Haukka J. The association of statin use with reduced incidence of venous thromboembolism: a population-based cohort study. *BMJ Open.* 2014 Nov 5;4(11):e005862. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2014-005862. PMID: 25377011; PMCID: PMC4225235.

³²Macedo AF, Taylor FC, Casas JP, Adler A, Prieto-Merino D, Ebrahim S. Unintended effects of statins from observational studies in the general population: systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Med.* 2014 Mar 22;12:51. doi: 10.1186/1741-7015-12-51. PMID: 24655568; PMCID: PMC3998050.

³³Khemasuwan D, Divietro ML, Tangdhanakanond K, Pomerantz SC, Eiger G. Statins decrease the occurrence of venous thromboembolism in patients with cancer. *Am J Med.* 2010 Jan;123(1):60-5. doi: 10.1016/j.amjmed.2009.05.025. PMID: 20102993.

³⁴Khemasuwan D, Chae YK, Gupta S, Carpio A, Yun JH, Neagu S, Lucca AB, Valsecchi ME, Mora JI. Dose-related effect of statins in venous thrombosis risk reduction. *Am J Med.* 2011 Sep;124(9):852-9. doi: 10.1016/j.amjmed.2011.04.019. Epub 2011 Jul 21. PMID: 21783169.

³⁵Nguyen CD, Andersson C, Jensen TB, Gjesing A, Schjerning Olsen AM, Malta Hansen C, Büller H, Torp-Pedersen C, Gislason GH. Statin treatment and risk of recurrent venous thromboembolism: a nationwide cohort study. *BMJ Open.* 2013 Nov 7;3(11):e003135. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2013-003135. PMID: 24202053; PMCID: PMC3822311.

³⁶Lötsch F, Königsbrügge O, Posch F, Zielinski C, Pabinger I, Ay C. Statins are associated with low risk of venous thromboembolism in patients with cancer: a prospective and observational cohort study. *Thromb Res.* 2014 Nov;134(5):1008-13. doi: 10.1016/j.thromres.2014.09.001. Epub 2014 Sep 6. PMID: 25234407.

³⁷Doggen CJ, Lemaitre RN, Smith NL, Heckbert SR, Psaty BM. HMG CoA reductase inhibitors and the risk of venous thrombosis among postmenopausal women. *J Thromb Haemost.* 2004 May;2(5):700-1. doi: 10.1111/j.1538-7836.2004.00696.x. PMID: 15099273.

³⁸Lacut K, Oger E, Le Gal G, Couturaud F, Louis S, Leroyer C, Mottier D. Statins but not fibrates are associated with a reduced risk of venous thromboembolism: a hospital-based case-control study. *Fundam Clin Pharmacol.* 2004 Aug;18(4):477-82. doi: 10.1111/j.1472-8206.2004.00252.x. PMID: 15312155.

³⁹Ramcharan AS, Van Stralen KJ, Snoep JD, Mantel-Teeuwisse AK, Rosendaal FR, Doggen CJ. HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors, other lipid-lowering medication, antiplatelet therapy, and the risk of venous thrombosis. *J Thromb Haemost.* 2009 Apr;7(4):514-20. doi: 10.1111/j.1538-7836.2008.03235.x. Epub 2008 Nov 24. PMID: 19036068.

⁴⁰Sørensen HT, Horvath-Puhó E, Sogaard KK, Christensen S, Johnsen SP, Thomsen RW, Prandoni P, Baron JA. Arterial cardiovascular events, statins, low-dose aspirin and subsequent risk of venous thromboembolism: a population-based case-control study. *J Thromb Haemost.* 2009 Apr;7(4):521-8. doi: 10.1111/j.1538-7836.2009.03279.x. Epub 2009 Jan 13. PMID: 19192118.

⁴¹El-Refai SM, Black EP, Adams VR, Talbert JC, Brown JD. Statin use and venous thromboembolism in cancer: A large, active comparator, propensity score matched cohort study. *Thromb Res.* 2017 Oct;158:49-58. doi: 10.1016/j.thromres.2017.08.001. Epub 2017 Aug 10. PMID: 28822240; PMCID: PMC5755594.

However, studies based on computerized databases in the United Kingdom found no relationship between statin use and risk of venous thrombosis.⁴² ·⁴³ Therefore, the need for randomized evidence⁴⁴ became apparent.

⁴²Yang CC, Jick SS, Jick H. Statins and the risk of idiopathic venous thromboembolism. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*. 2002 Jan;53(1):101-5. doi: 10.1046/j.0306-5251.2001.01523.x. PMID: 11849201; PMCID: PMC1874555.

⁴³Smeeth L, Douglas I, Hall AJ, Hubbard R, Evans S. Effect of statins on a wide range of health outcomes: a cohort study validated by comparison with randomized trials. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*. 2009 Jan;67(1):99-109. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2125.2008.03308.x. Epub 2008 Nov 5. PMID: 19006546; PMCID: PMC2668090.

⁴⁴Rahimi K, Bhala N, Kamphuisen P, Emberson J, Biere-Rafi S, Krane V, Robertson M, Wikstrand J, McMurray J. Effect of statins on venous thromboembolic events: a meta-analysis of published and unpublished evidence from randomised controlled trials. *PLoS Med*. 2012;9(9):e1001310. doi: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1001310. Epub 2012 Sep 18. PMID: 23028261; PMCID: PMC3445446.

2.1.10. HERS study, 2002

Herrington et al. ⁴⁵ randomized in the Heart and Estrogen/Progestin Replacement Study (HERS) 2763 postmenopausal women with CHD to receive either conjugated equine estrogens plus medroxyprogesterone acetate in one daily pill or placebo and monitored these women on average for 4.1 years (range 3.6 to 5.3 years). The rates of venous thromboembolic events were lower among statin users.

Table 14. Relationship: statin use and VTE (Study of Herrington et al., 2002).

		VTE		
		YES	NO	
Statin use	YES	9	995	1004
	NO	32	1435	1467
		41	2430	2471

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = -0,04940364$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00905393
p (EXCL) = 0,99635775
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,99103586
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,78048780

P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00905393
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_t) = 0,08067729
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_t) = 1,97560976
P Value (EXCL) = **0,00363563**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (9 / 2471) \times 100 = 0,36 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (995 / 2471) \times 100 = 40,27 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (32 / 2471) \times 100 = 1,30 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (1435 / 2471) \times 100 = 58,07 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (9 / 1004) \times 100 = 0,90 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (995 / 1004) \times 100 = 99,10 \%$
 $(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (32 / 1467) \times 100 = 2,18 \%$
 $(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (1435 / 1467) \times 100 = 97,82 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (9 / 41) \times 100 = 21,95 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (32 / 41) \times 100 = 78,05 \%$
 $(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (995 / 2430) \times 100 = 40,95 \%$
 $(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (1435 / 2430) \times 100 = 59,05 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (1004 / 2471) \times 100 = 40,63 \%$
 $(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (1467 / 2471) \times 100 = 59,37 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (41 / 2471) \times 100 = 1,66 \%$
 $(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (2430 / 2471) \times 100 = 98,34 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,41094995
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,53609511
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 58,91 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,40562186
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,45974638

STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU)= 0,57709429
p(IOI)= 0,38972076

Herrington et al. provided evidence of the exclusion relationship between statin use and VTE ($k = -0,04940364$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00905393) and $p(\text{EXCL}) = 0,99635775$ (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00363563). However, the study design with $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,38972076$ has been very unfair (Barukčić, 2019a). As a consequence, the exclusion relationship between statin use and VTE will be much stronger in reality than these data suggest.

⁴⁵Herrington DM, Vittinghoff E, Lin F, Fong J, Harris F, Hunninghake D, Bittner V, Schrott HG, Blumenthal RS, Levy R; HERS Study Group. Statin therapy, cardiovascular events, and total mortality in the Heart and Estrogen/Progestin Replacement Study (HERS). *Circulation*. 2002 Jun 25;105(25):2962-7. doi: 10.1161/01.cir.000019406.74017.b2. PMID: 12081988.

2.1.11. JUPITER study, 2009

Glynn et al. ⁴⁶ conducted a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, multicenter trial (Justification for the Use of Statins in Prevention: an Intervention Trial Evaluating Rosuvastatin (JUPITER) study) in order to investigate the effect of statin therapy on risk of venous thromboembolism. Symptomatic venous thromboembolism occurred in 34 participants in the rosuvastatin group (N=8901) and 60 participants in the placebo group (N=8901).

Table 15. Relationship: statin therapy and VTE (Study of Glynn et al., 2009).

		VTE		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy	YES	34	8867	8901
	NO	60	8841	8901
		94	17708	17802

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,02015230$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00468021
p (EXCL) = 0,99809010
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,99618020
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,63829787

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00468021
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 0,12987305
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 12,29787234
P Value (EXCL) = **0,00190808**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (34 / 17802) \times 100 = 0,19 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (8867 / 17802) \times 100 = 49,81 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (60 / 17802) \times 100 = 0,34 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (8841 / 17802) \times 100 = 49,66 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (34 / 8901) \times 100 = 0,38 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (8867 / 8901) \times 100 = 99,62 \%$
 $(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (60 / 8901) \times 100 = 0,67 \%$
 $(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (8841 / 8901) \times 100 = 99,33 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (34 / 94) \times 100 = 36,17 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (60 / 94) \times 100 = 63,83 \%$
 $(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (8867 / 17708) \times 100 = 50,07 \%$
 $(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (8841 / 17708) \times 100 = 49,93 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (8901 / 17802) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (8901 / 17802) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (94 / 17802) \times 100 = 0,53 \%$
 $(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (17708 / 17802) \times 100 = 99,47 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 0,56666667
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,72234366
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 43,33 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,56500507
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,27659574

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,49471969
p(IOI)= 0,49471969

Glynn et al. JUPITER trial showed a 43,33% decrease in the risk of VTE in the general population.

⁴⁶Glynn RJ, Danielson E, Fonseca FA, Genest J, Gotto AM Jr, Kastelein JJ, Koenig W, Libby P, Lorenzatti AJ, MacFadyen JG, Nordestgaard BG, Shepherd J, Willerson JT, Ridker PM. A randomized trial of rosuvastatin in the prevention of venous thromboembolism. *N Engl J Med.* 2009 Apr 30;360(18):1851-61. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa0900241. Epub 2009 Mar 29. PMID: 19329822; PMCID: PMC2710995.

Glynn et al. hypothesis generating trial provided evidence of the exclusion relationship between Statin therapy and VTE ($k = -0,02015230$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = $0,00468021$) and p (EXCL) = $0,998090102$ (P Value (EXCL) = $0,00190808$) even if the study design has been very unfair. It is common knowledge that the annual incidence of diagnosed venous thromboembolism (VTE) is about 1 to 2 events per 1000 of the general population.⁴⁷ The follow-up time of the JUPITER study has been about 5 years. The annual incidence of diagnosed venous thromboembolism according to JUPITER study is given as $\left(\frac{c}{NotA \times 5}\right) \times 1000 = \left(\frac{60}{8901 \times 5}\right) \times 1000 = 1.348163128$ or as 1.348163128 events per 1000 of the general population and not biased.⁴⁸ The data of the JUPITER study can very well be considered for our purposes. However, under conditions of fair study design, the relationship between statin and venous thromboembolism is much stronger than detected by the JUPITER study.

Table 16. Relationship: statin therapy and VTE (Study of Glynn et al. (fair study design), 2009).

		VTE		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy	YES	34	8867	8901
	NO	8867	1315419	1324286
		8901	1324286	1333187

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = -0,00287589$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = $0,00022519$
 p (EXCL) = $0,99997450$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) > 0,99618020$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) > 0,99618020$

P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = $0,00022519$
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = $0,12987305$
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = $0,12987305$
P Value (EXCL) = **$0,00002550$**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (34 / 1333187) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (8867 / 1333187) \times 100 = 0,67 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (8867 / 1333187) \times 100 = 0,67 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (1315419 / 1333187) \times 100 = 98,67 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (34 / 8901) \times 100 = 0,38 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (8867 / 8901) \times 100 = 99,62 \%$
 $(c/ not A) \times 100 = (8867 / 1324286) \times 100 = 0,67 \%$
 $(d/ not A) \times 100 = (1315419 / 1324286) \times 100 = 99,33 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (34 / 8901) \times 100 = 0,38 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (8867 / 8901) \times 100 = 99,62 \%$
 $(b/ not B) \times 100 = (8867 / 1324286) \times 100 = 0,67 \%$
 $(d/ not B) \times 100 = (1315419 / 1324286) \times 100 = 99,33 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (8901 / 1333187) \times 100 = 0,67 \%$
 $(not A/N) \times 100 = (1324286 / 1333187) \times 100 = 99,33 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (8901 / 1333187) \times 100 = 0,67 \%$
 $(not B/N) \times 100 = (1324286 / 1333187) \times 100 = 99,33 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = $0,57048627$
RR (sufficient condition) = $0,57048627$

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = $0,56883932$
Index of relationship (IOR) = $-0,42787308$

STUDY DESIGN.
 p (IOU) = $0,98664703$
 p (IOI) = $0,00000000$

Glynn et al. (fair study design) provided evidence of the exclusion relationship between statin therapy and VTE ($k = -0,00287589$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = $0,00022519$) and p (EXCL) = $0,999974497$ (P Value (EXCL) = $0,00002550$).

⁴⁷Kearon C. Epidemiology of venous thromboembolism. *Semin Vasc Med.* 2001;1(1):7-26. doi: 10.1055/s-2001-14668. PMID: 15199510.

⁴⁸see Kearon et al., 2001.

2.1.12. The study of Lötsch et al., 2014

Felix Lötsch et al. ⁴⁹ examined in a prospective **observational** cohort study whether statin-use is related with reduced risk of venous thromboembolism (followed for a maximum of 2 years).

Table 17. Relationship: statin use and VTE (Study of Lötsch et al. , 2014).

		VTE		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy	YES	6	164	170
	NO	107	1327	1434
		113	1491	1604

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,04729991$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,03348879
p (EXCL) = 0,99625935
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,96470588
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,94690265

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,03348879
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 0,21176471
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 0,31858407
P Value (EXCL) = **0,00373366**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (6 / 1604) \times 100 = 0,37 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (164 / 1604) \times 100 = 10,22 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (107 / 1604) \times 100 = 6,67 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (1327 / 1604) \times 100 = 82,73 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (6 / 170) \times 100 = 3,53 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (164 / 170) \times 100 = 96,47 \%$
 $(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (107 / 1434) \times 100 = 7,46 \%$
 $(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (1327 / 1434) \times 100 = 92,54 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (6 / 113) \times 100 = 5,31 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (107 / 113) \times 100 = 94,69 \%$
 $(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (164 / 1491) \times 100 = 11,00 \%$
 $(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (1327 / 1491) \times 100 = 89,00 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (170 / 1604) \times 100 = 10,60 \%$
 $(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (1434 / 1604) \times 100 = 89,40 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (113 / 1604) \times 100 = 7,04 \%$
 $(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (1491 / 1604) \times 100 = 92,96 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,47300715
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,48273257

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,45372692
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,49901093

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = 0,82356608
p(IOI) = 0,03553616

The data published by Lötsch et al. impress with a p(IOI) = 0,03553616 (Barukčić, 2019a) in the positive even if the incidence rate of VTE with $(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (107/1434) \times 100 = 7,46\%$ are a little bit high. Lötsch et al. did provide evidence of the exclusion relationship between Statin therapy and VTE ($k = -0,04729991$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,03348879) and p (EXCL) = 0,996259352 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00373366).

⁴⁹Lötsch F, Königsbrügge O, Posch F, Zielinski C, Pabinger I, Ay C. Statins are associated with low risk of venous thromboembolism in patients with cancer: a prospective and observational cohort study. *Thromb Res.* 2014 Nov;134(5):1008-13. doi: 10.1016/j.thromres.2014.09.001. Epub 2014 Sep 6. PMID: 25234407.

2.2. Methods

Over time, we have had to learn that our beliefs about the certainty or fallibility of scientific knowledge is more or less relative, too. It seems that the less reliable the applied scientific methods are, the shorter the lifespan of scientific knowledge is. Thus far, the importance of scientific methods for the reliable acquisition of knowledge cannot be overemphasised. Scientific methods which are common across science are equally one way of demarcating science from non-science. Logically sound definitions are another and very important aspect of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which a reliable scientific methodology is required to help us to *deal with erroneous definitions*⁵⁰ too.

2.2.1. Exclusion relationship

The probability of the exclusion relationship $p(\text{EXCL})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B)$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of an exclusion relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019b). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, left-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided left-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a positive causal relationship would contradict an exclusion relationship and vice versa.

2.2.2. Hyper-geometric distribution

In general, the probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable X is called a hyper-geometric distribution. In contrast to the binomial distribution, the hyper-geometric distribution is characterised by the lack of replacements. In this context, let N denote the population size, let A denote the number of success in the population, let B denote the number of draws (i.e. quantity drawn in each trial), let a itself denote the number of observed successes.

⁵⁰Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

Table 18. Hyper-geometric random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	A_t	FALSE	c	d
		B	<u>B</u>	N

With this in mind, the probability mass function of the hyper-geometric distribution (see Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899), denoted as $p(X = a)$, is defined as

$$p(X = a) = \frac{\binom{A}{a} \binom{N-A}{B-a}}{\binom{N}{B}} = \frac{\binom{B}{a} \binom{N-B}{A-a}}{\binom{N}{A}} \quad (1)$$

The hyper-geometric distribution, a probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable, has several properties which unfortunately cannot be discussed in detail here. A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (2)$$

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is less than or equal to some specified upper limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^a \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (3)$$

2.2.3. Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test proposed by Fisher (1934) in the fifth edition of *Statistical Methods for Research Workers* (see Fisher, 1934, pp. 99-103) is a statistical significance test which is often used in

the analysis of contingency tables while applying the hyper-geometric distribution ⁵¹. This statistical methodology opens up the possibility to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. Strangely enough, it is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (see also [Fisher, 1935](#)) for a sample which is very small. However, it is necessary to point out that Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes without any restriction. Fisher's Exact Test is using the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H0: (null hypothesis)

The two random variables are independent.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

The two random variables are not independent.

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability denotes whether a hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit and less than or equal to some specified upper limit. The P Value of an one-sided right tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (4)$$

The P Value of an one-sided left tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (5)$$

2.2.4. The Chi-square goodness of fit test

The χ^2 distribution is one of the most versatile distributions in applied statistics. Historically, the χ^2 distribution has been described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (see [Helmert, 1876](#)). Later, the χ^2 distribution has been rediscovered by Karl Pearson (see [Pearson, 1900](#)) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The Chi-square goodness of fit test checks the agreement or conformity or consistency between a hypothetical or a theoretical distribution given in a population and a sample distribution drawn from such a population. Karl Pearson's approximate formula for calculating a Chi-square statistic may be shown schematically as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(\text{Observed}_t - E(\text{Observed}_t))^2}{E(\text{Observed}_t)} \quad (6)$$

Some author prefer the use of Yate's correction for continuity (see [Yates, 1934](#)) when there is one degree of freedom.

⁵¹Kim HY. Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2017 May;42(2):152-155. doi: 10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152. Epub 2017 Mar 30. PMID: 28503482; PMCID: PMC5426219.

Example

Let us illustrate the Chi-square goodness of fit test by an example. A random sample of 100 people with 44 men and 56 women is drawn from a certain population. It is assumed that men and women are equal in frequency in the population. The theoretical frequencies of 50 men and 50 women is compared with the observed number of men and women.

Bernoulli trial t	Event	Observed O_t	Expected $E(O_t)$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2 / E(O_t)$
1	Men	44	50	36	0.72
2	Women	56	50	36	0.72
Rows = 2		Sample size =	100	Chi-square =	1.44

There are rows - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1 degree of freedom and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A $\chi^2 = 1.44$ is less than 3.84 and not significant. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis: the sample distribution is consistent with a theoretical distribution given in population. In other words, men and women are more or less equal in frequency in the population. In the case of a necessary condition relationship (SINE), our hypotheses could be:

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) \geq 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

However, a probability cannot be greater than 1. Therefore, the hypotheses are more precisely

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) = 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

Accepting H_0 is equivalent with rejecting H_A and vice versa. Accepting H_A is equivalent with rejecting H_0 . Assumed that the degree of freedom is 1 and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A χ^2 of a necessary condition relationship which is less than 3.84 is not significant. Therefore, we would have to accept the null hypothesis: a sample distribution would be consistent with a theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship given in population. However, Chi-square like any statistics has its limitations. The Chi-square is highly sensitive to sample size. The Chi-square goodness of fit test might give inaccurate results when the sample size is too small ($N < 50$) or too large (see [Bagozzi, 1981](#)) (G-square test). When the sample sizes are too small, Fisher's exact test of independence can be considered too.

2.2.5. The P Value of extreme events

There are circumstances where N Bernoulli trials (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) are performed while an event X_t should occur at each single Bernoulli trial t . The probability of a single event is given as

$$p(X_t) = \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} \quad (7)$$

The probability of a single anti-event or non-event et cetera is given as

$$p(\underline{X}_t) = 1 - p(X_t) = 1 - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t}{X_t} - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{X_t} = \frac{E(\underline{X}_t)}{X_t} \quad (8)$$

As soon, as the number of Bernoulli trials increases, the probability of a single event follows approximately (see [Barukčić, 2019b](#), p. 1844) as

$$p(X_t) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(\underline{X}_t)}{N}\right)\right) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{N}\right)\right) \quad (9)$$

Under conditions where $X_t = N$, equation 9 simplifies to

$$p(X_t) = \exp(-(1 - p(X_t))) \quad (10)$$

There are single events or relationships where the probability of an event or of a relationship is constant from trial to trial and equals $p(X_t) = 1$ in the population. Nonetheless, for many reasons, such extreme events like the necessary condition relationship, the sufficient condition relationship, the exclusion relationship et cetera does not necessarily have to be given in a sample drawn from a population too. Under these circumstances, there is a need to proof whether there is a significant difference between the sample probability or proportion and the population probability or proportion or is the difference due to chance. In other words, does the sample probability or proportion deviate significantly from the population probability or proportion which itself is equal to 1. We perform a one-sided left tailed statistical test. A probability of a single event cannot be greater than 1, therefore our hypotheses are:

$$H_0: p(X_t) \leq 0.999\ 999 \dots \text{ vs. } H_A: p(X_t) > 0.999\ 999 \dots$$

In general, the expectation value of extreme events or relationship with $p(X_t) = 1$ at every single Bernoulli trial t is $E(X) = N \times p(X_t) = N \times 1 = N$. Thus far, under circumstances where $N = E(X)$, the hypotheses before simplify to

$$H_0: E(X) \leq N-1 \text{ vs. } H_A: E(X) > N-1$$

However, it is to be noted that $N > N-1$. The cumulative distribution function is given as

$$p(E(X_t))\text{cdf} = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots p(X_t = (N - 1)) + p(X_t = N) = +1 \quad (11)$$

It is

$$p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots p(X_t = (N - 1)) \quad (12)$$

and

$$p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = p(E(X_t) = N) \quad (13)$$

The P Value of a one-sided left (see [Barukčić, 2019b](#), p. 1846) tailed statistical test is given as

$$\text{P Value}_{\text{one sided left tailed}} = p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) \quad (14)$$

We have reasons to believe that a left tailed P Value which is greater than or equal to the significance level α or P Value $\geq \alpha$, is providing some evidence to accept the null hypothesis: The sample distribution deviates significantly from the population distribution. Under such circumstances, the sample data would not support a claim that i.e. there is a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship or *conditio per quam* relationship or exclusion relationship et cetera. However, a left tailed P Value which is less than the significance level α or P Value $< \alpha$, urges us to reject the null hypothesis and to accept the alternative hypothesis. In other words, there is no deviation of the probability found in a sample distribution from the the probability of a population distribution. It is $p(X_t) = 1$ with a certain P Value.

2.2.6. Bonferroni correction

Multiple testing at a certain level of significance α might amplify the probability of false-positive findings. In other words, the more inferences are made (on a certain data body i. e. subgroup analyses et cetera), the more likely erroneous inferences might realise. At the end, several independent or dependent statistical tests performed simultaneously (on the same data body) can induce the so called family-wise error rate (FWER) or multiple testing problem. The family-wise error rate or multiple testing problem (see [Tukey, 1994](#)) is ascribed to John Wilder Tukey (1915 – 2000), an American mathematician and statistician. The probability that at least one null hypothesis out of k null hypotheses tested is falsely rejected is no longer equal to the overall significance level α but equal to

$$\alpha_{\text{FWER}} = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^k \quad (15)$$

As a consequence, a higher significance threshold for an individual hypothesis, denoted as α_i , is demanded. Various statistical techniques have been developed to address this problem. The Bonferroni multiple-comparison correction (see [Bonferroni, 1936](#); [Dunn, 1961](#)) is one of the solutions proposed to compensate for the number of inferences being made.

Example

An investigation is testing $m = 20$ hypotheses with a desired $\alpha = 0.05$. Under these circumstances, the Bonferroni correction might be of appropriate use. Each individual hypothesis should be tested at a single level of significance α_i given as

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\alpha}{m} = \frac{0,05}{2} = 0,025 \quad (16)$$

where m is the total number of hypotheses tested and α is the overall significance level. By requiring a stricter significance threshold, **an inflation of false positive results** can be prevented. In the context of further scientific development, there have been several trials to improve the Bonferroni method. One of these attempts is the so called Rom's Method published 1990 by Rom (see [Rom, 1990](#)) himself.

2.2.7. Bernoulli distribution

A single event distribution is more or less a discrete probability distribution of any random variable X which takes a certain (observer independent) single value X_t at a **Bernoulli trial** (Uspensky, 1937, p. 45) (period of time) t with the probability $p(X_t)$. The same random variable X takes a certain single anti value \bar{X}_t at a Bernoulli trial (period of time) t with the probability $1-p(X_t)$. There are conditions in nature where a random variable X can take only the values either $+0$ or $+1$ (see Birnbaum, 1961). Under these conditions, the random variable X takes the value 1 with probability $p(X_t = +1)$ and the value 0 with probability $q(X_t = +0) = 1 - p(X_t = +1)$ while the single event distribution passes over into the **Bernoulli distribution**, named after Swiss mathematician Jacob Bernoulli (Bernoulli, 1713). Less formally, many times, the Bernoulli distribution is represented by a (possibly not biased) coin toss where 1 and 0 would represent ‘heads’ and ‘tails’ (or vice versa), respectively. However, the relationship between random variables (Gosset, 1914) can be investigated by many (Gosset, 1908) methods, including the tools of probability theory, too.

Definition 2.1 (Two by two table of single event random variables).

The two by two or contingency table which has been introduced by Karl Pearson (Pearson, 1904b) in 1904 harbours still a large variety of topics and debates. Central to this is the problem to apply the laws of classical logic on data sets, which concerns the justification of inferences which extrapolate from sample data to general facts. Nevertheless, a contingency table is still an appropriate theoretical model too for studying the relationships between random variables, including *Bernoulli* (Bernoulli, 1713) (i.e. $+0/+1$) distributed random variables existing or occurring at the same *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t .

In this context, let a random variable A at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t , denoted by A_t , indicate a risk factor, a condition, a cause et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(A_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t . Let $E(A_t)$ denote the expectation value of A_t . In general it is

$$p(A_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \quad (17)$$

The expectation value $E(A_t)$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv A_t \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t)) \\ &\equiv (A_t \times p(a_t)) + (A_t \times p(b_t)) \\ &\equiv E(a_t) + E(b_t) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Under conditions of $+0/+1$ distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv p(A_t) \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{A}_t) \equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \quad (20)$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{A}_t)$ is given as

$$\begin{aligned} E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\ &\equiv A_t \times (p(c_t) + p(d_t)) \\ &\equiv (A_t \times p(c_t)) + (A_t \times p(d_t)) \\ &\equiv E(c_t) + E(d_t) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\ &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\ &\equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \\ &\equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Let a random variable B at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t , denoted by B_t , indicate an outcome, a conditioned, an effect et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(B_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t . Let $E(B_t)$ denote the expectation value of B_t . In general it is

$$p(B_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) \quad (23)$$

The expectation value $E(B_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned} E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\ &\equiv B_t \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t)) \\ &\equiv (B_t \times p(a_t)) + (B_t \times p(c_t)) \\ &\equiv E(a_t) + E(c_t) \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\ &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(B_t) \\ &\equiv p(B_t) \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{B}_t) \equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \quad (26)$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{B}_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned} E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv B_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\ &\equiv B_t \times (p(b_t) + p(d_t)) \\ &\equiv (B_t \times p(b_t)) + (B_t \times p(d_t)) \\ &\equiv E(b_t) + E(d_t) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv B_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

Let $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Let $p(b_t) = p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Let $p(c_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0+1) \times (+0+1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

Let $p(d_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0+1) \times (+0+1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

In general, it is

$$p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv +1 \tag{37}$$

Table 19 provide us with an overview of the definitions above.

Table 19. The two by two table of Bernoulli random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

In our understanding, it is

$$p(B_t) + p(\Lambda_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(\Lambda_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \equiv p(A_t) \tag{38}$$

or

$$p(c_t) + p(\Lambda_t) \equiv p(b_t) \tag{39}$$

Under conditions of Einstein's general theory of relativity, Λ denotes the Einstein cosmological (Einstein, 1917) 'constant'.

2.2.8. Binomial random variables

The binomial (see [Pearson, 1895](#), p. 351) distribution (see [Cramér, 1937](#)) with parameters n and p has been developed by the Swiss mathematician Jakob Bernoulli (1655-1705) in a proof published in his 1713 book *Ars Conjectandi* (see [Bernoulli, 1713](#)) Part 1. In probability theory and statistics, the probability of getting exactly k successes in n independent Bernoulli trials is given by the probability mass function as

$$p(X_t = k) \equiv \binom{n}{k} \cdot p^k \cdot q^{n-k} \quad (40)$$

is $\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$ the binomial coefficient while the cumulative distribution function is given as

$$p(X_t \leq k) \equiv 1 - p(X_t > k) \equiv \sum_{t=0}^k \binom{n}{t} \cdot p^t \cdot q^{n-t} \quad (41)$$

or as

$$p(X_t > k) \equiv 1 - p(X_t \leq k) \equiv 1 - \sum_{t=0}^k \binom{n}{t} \cdot p^t \cdot q^{n-t} \quad (42)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(X_t < k) \equiv 1 - p(X_t \geq k) \equiv \sum_{t=0}^{k-1} \binom{n}{t} \cdot p^t \cdot q^{n-t} \quad (43)$$

or

$$p(X_t \geq k) \equiv 1 - p(X_t < k) \equiv 1 - \sum_{t=0}^{k-1} \binom{n}{t} \cdot p^t \cdot q^{n-t} \quad (44)$$

The binomial distribution is the mathematical foundation of a binomial test. The random variable X_t is counting for different things. The discrete geometric (see [Feller, 1950](#), p. 61) distribution describes under certain circumstances the number of Bernoulli trials needed to get one success. The probability that the first occurrence of success requires k independent trials, each with success probability p , is given by the equation

$$p(X_t = k) \equiv p \cdot q^{k-1} \quad (45)$$

The negative (see [Fisher, 1941](#); [Haldane, 1941](#)) binomial probability is a discrete probability distribution which defines the number of successes (k) in a sequence of independent and identically distributed Bernoulli trials (n) before a specified (non-random) number of failures (denoted r) occurs. The probability mass function of the negative binomial distribution is

$$p(X_t = r) \equiv \binom{k+r-1}{k-1} p^k \cdot q^r \quad (46)$$

where k is the number of successes, r is the number of failures, and p is the probability of success.

Definition 2.2 (Expectation value and variance of a binomial random variable).

The variance (see [Pearson, 1904a](#), p. 66) of the binomial distribution with parameters n , the number of independent experiments each asking a yes–no question and p , the probability of a single event, is defined in contrast to Pearson (see [Barukčić, 2022](#)) as

$$\sigma(X_t)^2 \equiv N \times N \times p(X_t) \times (1 - p(X_t)) \quad (47)$$

Definition 2.3 (Two by two table of Binomial random variables).

Let $a, b, c, d, A, \underline{A}, B,$ and \underline{B} denote expectation values. Under conditions where *the probability of an event, an outcome, a success et cetera is constant from Bernoulli trial to Bernoulli trial t* , it is

$$\begin{aligned} A &= N \times E(A_t) \\ &\equiv N \times (A_t \times p(A_t)) \\ &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(B_t)) \\ &\equiv N \times p(A_t) \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} B &= N \times E(B_t) \\ &\equiv N \times (B_t \times p(B_t)) \\ &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(c_t)) \\ &\equiv N \times p(B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

where N might denote the population or even the sample size. Furthermore, it is

$$a \equiv N \times (E(A_t)) \equiv N \times (p(A_t)) \quad (50)$$

and

$$b \equiv N \times (E(B_t)) \equiv N \times (p(B_t)) \quad (51)$$

and

$$c \equiv N \times (E(c_t)) \equiv N \times (p(c_t)) \quad (52)$$

and

$$d \equiv N \times (E(d_t)) \equiv N \times (p(d_t)) \quad (53)$$

and

$$a + b + c + d \equiv A + \underline{A} \equiv B + \underline{B} \equiv N \quad (54)$$

Table 20 provide us again an overview of a two by two contingency (see also [Pearson, 1904b](#), p. 33) table of Binomial random variables.

Table 20. The two by two table of Binomial random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	a	b	A
	FALSE	c	d	<u>A</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

“Such a table is termed a contingency table, and the ultimate scientific statement of description of the relation between two things can always be thrown back upon such a contingency table Once the reader realizes the nature of such a table, he will have grasped the essence of the conception of association between cause and effect, and the nature of its ideal limit in causation. ”

(see also [Pearson, 1911](#), p. 159)

3. Results

3.1. Endoxaban does not protect people against venous thromboembolism

Theorem 1 (Endoxaban and venous thromboembolism).

Null-hypothesis (H_0):

Endoxaban does exclude venous thromboembolism is true.

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

*Endoxaban does exclude venous thromboembolism is **not** true.*

Proof by experiment/induction. The data of the study of Giugliano et al. ⁵² have been re-analysed. The data of Giugliano et al. do not provide us with a very convincing evidence of the exclusion relationship between endoxaban and stroke. The **Null-hypothesis (H_0) Endoxaban does exclude venous thromboembolism is true** cannot be accepted ($k = -0,01266796$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,07199244 and p (EXCL) = 0,980029849 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,01977207) while the sample size has been $N = 14071$) and is rejected (P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,07199244). □

3.1.0.1. Fisher's one sided left tailed exact test The hyper-geometric distribution (HGD) describes the probability of x successes in N **draws without replacement** while the same distribution is valid for all sample sizes. In contrast to the hyper-geometric distribution, the binomial distribution describes the probability of x successes in N **draws with replacement**. The one sided left tailed P Value is used when the alternative to independence is that there is a **negative relationship** between the variables investigated. Fisher's exact test (Fisher, 1935) is a statistical significance test which is based on the hyper-geometric distribution and enable us to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. The left tailed P Value (no replacement, hyper-geometric distribution) (see also Fisher's exact test (see also Barnard, 1945; Boschloo, 1970; Fisher, 1935)) is calculated as follows:

⁵²Giugliano RP, Ruff CT, Braunwald E, Murphy SA, Wiviott SD, Halperin JL, Waldo AL, Ezekowitz MD, Weitz JI, Špinar J, Ruzyllo W, Ruda M, Koretsune Y, Betcher J, Shi M, Grip LT, Patel SP, Patel I, Hanyok JJ, Mercuri M, Antman EM; ENGAGE AF-TIMI 48 Investigators. Edoxaban versus warfarin in patients with atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med.* 2013 Nov 28;369(22):2093-104. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1310907. Epub 2013 Nov 19. PMID: 24251359.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(X \leq a) &= \sum_{i=0}^a \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^{281} \frac{\binom{7035}{i} \binom{14071-7035}{598-i}}{\binom{14071}{598}} \quad (55) \\
 &= 0,0719924417 \\
 &= \text{P Value (one sided left tailed)}
 \end{aligned}$$

In fact, the use of endoxaban and stroke are independent of each other (**P Value (one sided left tailed) = 0,0719924417**), which in the case of an exclusion relationship cannot be. Nonetheless, critical comments like the sample size with $N = 14071$ is too large for Fisher's-exact test are conceivable. As a result, Fisher's-exact test cannot be applied to this data body. Such throwing of sand in the eyes of the reader may confuse non-experts, but as experts surely know are without any mathematical foundation. The conclusion is inescapable, endoxaban does not protect people against stroke (**P Value (one sided left tailed) = 0,0719924417**).

3.2. Statins does protect people against venous thromboembolism

Theorem 2 (Statins and venous thromboembolism).

Null-hypothesis (H_0):

Statins does exclude venous thromboembolism is true.

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

Statins does exclude venous thromboembolism is not true.

Proof by experiment/induction. The data of the randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, multi-center trial of Glynn et al. ⁵³ have been re-analysed. The data of Glynn et al. do provide us with a very convincing evidence of the exclusion relationship between statins and VTE. The **Null-hypothesis (H_0) statins does exclude venous thromboembolism is true and need to be accepted** ($k = -0,02015230$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00468021) and p (EXCL) = 0,998090102 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00190808).

□

3.2.0.1. Fisher's one sided left tailed exact test The left tailed P Value (no replacement, hypergeometric distribution) (see also Fisher's exact test (see also [Barnard, 1945](#); [Boschloo, 1970](#); [Fisher, 1935](#))) is calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(X \leq a) &= \sum_{i=0}^a \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^{34} \frac{\binom{8901}{i} \binom{17802-8901}{94-i}}{\binom{17802}{94}} \quad (56) \\
 &= 0,0046802132 \\
 &= \text{P Value (one sided left tailed)}
 \end{aligned}$$

The **Null-hypothesis (H_0) statins does exclude venous thromboembolism is true and need to be accepted** (p (EXCL) = 0,998090102; P Value (EXCL) = 0,00190808), even if the study design with **$p(\text{IOI}) = 0,49471969$** has been very unfair.

⁵³Glynn RJ, Danielson E, Fonseca FA, Genest J, Gotto AM Jr, Kastelein JJ, Koenig W, Libby P, Lorenzatti AJ, MacFadyen JG, Nordestgaard BG, Shepherd J, Willerson JT, Ridker PM. A randomized trial of rosuvastatin in the prevention of venous thromboembolism. *N Engl J Med.* 2009 Apr 30;360(18):1851-61. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa0900241. Epub 2009 Mar 29. PMID: 19329822; PMCID: PMC2710995.

4. Discussion

Venous thromboembolism (i.e., pulmonary embolism and deep vein thrombosis) are very common events in the population^{54, 55, 56}, yet our possibilities to safely prevent it, are limited. In general, venous and arterial thrombosis seem to share some common risk factors⁵⁷. Various non-randomised studies with very heterogenous study design provided somewhat contradictory evidence for the effect of statins on venous thromboembolism, and so the exclusion relationship between statin use and VTE may partly (or even wholly) reflect the play of chance. However, in 2009, the JUPITER trial, provided direct randomised evidence that statin use might reduce venous thromboembolic events. This study has been unjustly criticized. The JUPITER trial was based on relatively few patients with a venous thromboembolic event (34 versus 60) and uncertainty about the exclusion relationship between statin use and VTE grew. Unfortunately, it was not recognized that the prevalence of VTE in the JUPITER placebo group was very reliably confirmed. In other words, we can rely on the data as published by this randomized, (placebo) controlled trial. Glynn et al.⁵⁸ provided highly significant evidence of the exclusion relationship between statin therapy and VTE ($k = -0,02015230$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00468021) with p (EXCL) = 0,998090102 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00190808). In other words, the efficacy of a long-term therapy with statins against venous thromboembolism (p (EXCL) = **0,998090102**; P Value (EXCL) = 0,00190808) is nearly comparable with the efficacy of a vaccination with Pfizer/Biontech's mRNA vaccine against Covid 19 (p (EXCL)= $1-(8/43448) = \mathbf{0,999815872}$; P Value = 0,000184128).^{59, 60} In other words, statins are protecting people against venous thromboembolism (see table 15) better than endoxaban (see table 8; see theorem 1).

⁵⁴Silverstein MD, Heit JA, Mohr DN, Petterson TM, O'Fallon WM, Melton LJ 3rd. Trends in the incidence of deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism: a 25-year population-based study. *Arch Intern Med.* 1998 Mar 23;158(6):585-93. doi: 10.1001/archinte.158.6.585. PMID: 9521222.

⁵⁵Heit JA. Venous thromboembolism: disease burden, outcomes and risk factors. *J Thromb Haemost.* 2005 Aug;3(8):1611-7. doi: 10.1111/j.1538-7836.2005.01415.x. PMID: 16102026.

⁵⁶Naess IA, Christiansen SC, Romundstad P, Cannegieter SC, Rosendaal FR, Hammerstrøm J. Incidence and mortality of venous thrombosis: a population-based study. *J Thromb Haemost.* 2007 Apr;5(4):692-9. doi: 10.1111/j.1538-7836.2007.02450.x. PMID: 17367492.

⁵⁷Agno W, Becattini C, Brighton T, Selby R, Kamphuisen PW. Cardiovascular risk factors and venous thromboembolism: a meta-analysis. *Circulation.* 2008 Jan 1;117(1):93-102. doi: 10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.107.709204. Epub 2007 Dec 17. PMID: 18086925.

⁵⁸Glynn RJ, Danielson E, Fonseca FA, Genest J, Gotto AM Jr, Kastelein JJ, Koenig W, Libby P, Lorenzatti AJ, MacFadyen JG, Nordestgaard BG, Shepherd J, Willerson JT, Ridker PM. A randomized trial of rosuvastatin in the prevention of venous thromboembolism. *N Engl J Med.* 2009 Apr 30;360(18):1851-61. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa0900241. Epub 2009 Mar 29. PMID: 19329822; PMCID: PMC2710995.

⁵⁹Polack FP, Thomas SJ, Kitchin N, Absalon J, Gurtman A, Lockhart S, Perez JL, Pérez Marc G, Moreira ED, Zerbini C, Bailey R, Swanson KA, Roychoudhury S, Koury K, Li P, Kalina WV, Cooper D, Frenck RW Jr, Hammitt LL, Türeci Ö, Nell H, Schaefer A, Ünal S, Tresnan DB, Mather S, Dormitzer PR, Şahin U, Jansen KU, Gruber WC; C4591001 Clinical Trial Group. Safety and Efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 Vaccine. *N Engl J Med.* 2020 Dec 31;383(27):2603-2615. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2034577. Epub 2020 Dec 10. PMID: 33301246; PMCID: PMC7745181.

⁶⁰Barukčić, Ilija. (2021). COVID-19 vaccines - a great leap forward?. *Causation*, 6(12), 5–53. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779506>, p. 42.

5. Conclusion

Taking into account the data presented, we come to the following conclusion.

‘Endoxaban and other NOACs do not protect people against stroke as desired and suspected.’

Acknowledgments

No funding or any financial support by a third party was received.

Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

References

- Richard P. Bagozzi. Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: A comment. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(3):375–381, 1981. ISSN 00222437. URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3150979>.
- George Alfred Barnard. A new test for 2×2 tables. *Nature*, 156(3954):177, 1945. doi: 10.1038/156177a0.
- Ilija Barukčić. The Mathematical Formula of the Causal Relationship k. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 6(2):45–65, January 2016. doi: 10.17706/ijapm.2016.6.2.45-65. [IJAPM](#). Free full text: [IAP](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Index of Independence. *Modern Health Science*, 2(2):1–25, 10 2019a. ISSN 2576-7305. doi: 10.30560/mhs.v2n2p1. URL <https://j.ideasspread.org/index.php/mhs/article/view/331>. [Modern Health Science](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. The P Value of likely extreme events. *International Journal of Current Science Research*, 5(11):1841–1861, 2019b. [IJCSR ZENODO](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Causal relationship k. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology IJMTT*, 66(10):76–115, 2020. URL <http://www.ijmttjournal.org/archive/ijmtt-v66i10p512>. [IJMTT](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Mutually exclusive events. *Causation*, 16(11):5–57, November 2021a. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5746415. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5746415>. [Zenodo](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. The causal relationship k. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 336:09032, 2021b. ISSN 2261-236X. doi: 10.1051/mateconf/202133609032. [CSCNS2020](#). [Web of Science](#). Free full text: [EDP Sciences](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Variance of binomial distribution. *Causation*, 17(1):5–22, 1 2022. URL <https://www.causation.eu/index.php/causation/article/view/7>.
- Jacobi Bernoulli. *Ars conjectandi, Opus posthumus: Accedit Tractatus de seriebus infinitis ; et epistola Gallice scripta De Ludo Pilae Reticularis*. Impensis Thurnisiorum [Tournes], fratrum, Basileae (Basel, Suisse), January 1713. doi: 10.3931/e-rara-9001. Free full text: [e-rara](#), [Zurich](#), [CH](#).
- Alan Birnbaum. On the foundations of statistical inference: Binary experiments. *Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 32(1):340–341, 1961. [jstor](#).
- Carlo Emilio Bonferroni. Teoria statistica delle classi e calcolo delle probabilita. *Pubblicazioni del R Istituto Superiore di Scienze Economiche e Commerciali di Firenze*, 8:3–62, 1936.
- RD Boschloo. Raised conditional level of significance for the 2×2 -table when testing the equality of two probabilities. *Statistica Neerlandica*, 24, 1970. doi: 10.1111/j.1467-9574.1970.tb00104.x.
- Ji Y Chong and Ralph L Sacco. Risk factors for stroke, assessing risk, and the mass and high-risk approaches for stroke prevention. *CONTINUUM: Lifelong Learning in Neurology*, 11(4):18–34, 2005.
- Harald Cramér. *Random variables and probability distributions*. Cambridge University Press, 1937.
- Olive Jean Dunn. Multiple comparisons among means. *Journal of the American statistical association*, 56(293):52–64, 1961.
- Albert Einstein. Kosmologische betrachtungen zur allgemeinen relativitätstheorie. *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (Berlin)*, page 142–152, 1917. [ECHO](#).
- William Feller. *Introduction to Probability Theory and its Applications. Volume I & II.*, volume 1. John Wiley and Sons Inc., 1st edition edition, 1 1950. [John Wiley and Sons Inc](#).
- Ronald Aylmer Fisher. On the Interpretation of Chi square from Contingency Tables, and the Calculation of P. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 85(1):87–94, 1922. ISSN 0952-8385. doi: 10.2307/2340521. [JSTOR](#).
- Ronald Aylmer Fisher. *Statistical methods for research workers*. Number 5 in Biological Monographs and manuals. Oliver and Boyd, Edinburgh, 1934. [Archive.org](#).

Ronald Aylmer Fisher. The negative binomial distribution. *Annals of Eugenics*, 11(1):182–187, 1941. ISSN 2050-1439. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-1809.1941.tb02284.x. [Wiley Online Library](#).

Sir Ronald Aylmer Fisher. *The Design Of Experiments*. Oliver and Boyd, Edinburgh, 1935.

H. T. Gonin. XIV. The use of factorial moments in the treatment of the hypergeometric distribution and in tests for regression. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 21(139):215–226, January 1936. ISSN 1941-5982. doi: 10.1080/14786443608561573. [Taylor and Francis](#).

William Sealy Gosset. The probable error of a mean. *Biometrika*, 6(1):1–25, 1908. ISSN 0006-3444. doi: 1. [JSTOR](#).

William Sealy Gosset. The elimination of spurious correlation due to position in time or space. *Biometrika*, 10(1):179–180, 1914. ISSN 0006-3444. doi: 10.2307/2331746. [JSTOR](#).

C. B. Granger, J. H. Alexander, J. J. McMurray, R. D. Lopes, E. M. Hylek, M. Hanna, H. R. Al-Khalidi, J. Ansell, D. Atar, A. Avezum, M. C. Bahit, R. Diaz, J. D. Easton, J. A. Ezekowitz, G. Flaker, D. Garcia, M. Geraldles, B. J. Gersh, S. Golitsyn, S. Goto, A. G. Hermosillo, S. H. Hohnloser, J. Horowitz, P. Mohan, P. Jansky, B. S. Lewis, J. L. Lopez-Sendon, P. Pais, A. Parkhomenko, F. W. Verheugt, J. Zhu, L. Wallentin, C. B. Granger, L. Wallentin, J. H. Alexander, J. Ansell, R. Diaz, J. D. Easton, B. J. Gersh, M. Hanna, J. Horowitz, E. M. Hylek, J. J. McMurray, P. Mohan, F. W. Verheugt, R. Diaz, M. C. Bahit, P. Aylward, J. Amerena, K. Huber, J. Bartunek, A. Avezum, J. A. Ezekowitz, P. Dorian, F. Lanus, L. Lisheng, J. Zhu, D. Isaza, P. Jansky, S. Husted, V. P. Harjola, P. G. Steg, S. H. Hohnloser, M. Keltai, P. Pais, D. Xavier, B. S. Lewis, R. De Caterina, S. Goto, A. G. Hermosillo, A. M. Alings, D. Atar, L. Segura, W. Ruzyllo, D. Vinereanu, S. Varshavsky, S. Golitsyn, B. H. Oh, P. Commerford, J. L. Lopez-Sendon, M. Rosenquist, C. Erol, J. J. McMurray, A. Parkhomenko, G. Flaker, D. Garcia, M. A. Pfeffer, H. C. Diener, A. Maggioni, S. Pocock, J. L. Rouleau, G. Wyse, L. Hatch, M. Banks, A. Handler, H. Yang, J. Garg, K. Griffith, A. Burr, T. Dremsizov, J. Vidal, S. Hinton, L. Rossi, F. Fiedorek, S. Nepal, R. Croop, A. Delvaux, S. Mullin, N. Arotzky, E. Nemeth, A. Bastien, R. Wolf, N. Jackson, R. Braceras, J. H. Alexander, S. Al-Khatib, R. D. Lopes, C. Held, E. M. Hylek, C. Bushnell, A. Terent, S. Leonardi, S. Subherwal, Z. Eapen, J. Vavalle, A. Zomorodi, B. Kolls, J. Berger, J. Vergara, D. Parikh, S. Zia, G. Stashenko, C. Lombardi, R. Matthews, E. Hagstrom, A. Akerblom, C. Varenhorst, S. G. Bernntsson, A. Stenborg, E. Lundstrom, H. Guimaraes, U. Flato, S. Nacif, P. Barros, L. Echenique, P. Rodrigues, L. Armaganjian, A. C. Lopes, A. Albrecht, M. Vico, I. Mackinnon, D. Vogel, M. Vico, A. Gabito, A. Cassettari, C. Zaidman, O. a. A. Hrabar, H. Jure, H. Lastiri, C. Poy, A. Caccavo, C. Cuneo, H. Colombo, F. Rolandi, A. Hershson, M. Garrido, A. Sanchez, M. L. Bruno, D. Piskorz, J. Cuadrado, E. Hasbani, J. Serra, L. Cartasegna, P. Schygiel, C. Muratore, J. Marino, M. I. Sosa Liprandi, R. A. Guerrero, H. Ramos, D. Mercado, L. Guzman, C. Beneitez, J. Estepo, R. Torrijos, E. Retyk, N. Vita, H. Luciardi, M. Casey, S. Orlando, M. B. Labarta, D. Santos, J. Amerena, P. Purnell, J. Horowitz, H. Salem, A. Liu, L. Zimmet, S. Roger, F. de Looze, F. de Looze, R. Lehman, F. de Looze, B. Jackson, D. Ashby, W. Heddle, J. Rogers, D. Brieger, P. Martin, D. Cross, D. Walters, J. Waites, J. Counsell, A. Lowy, F. de Looze, K. Huber, F. Stockenhuber, B. Pieske, H. Striekwold, B. Wollaert, H. Nachtergaele, J. Vijgen, D. El Allaf, G. Mairesse, G. Boxho, P. P. De Deyn, M. Vanderheyden, O. Semeraro, P. Desfontaines, J. Leroy, F. Provenier, B. Bruneel, M. Vrolix, A. Peeters, O. Deceuninck, J. F. Saraiva, G. Reis, P. Rossi, S. Zimmermann, J. Jaber, R. Botelho, E. Manenti, J. Jorge, L. Maia, P. es, F. V. Guimaraes Filho, M. Fichino, A. De Paola, C. K. do Brasil, D. Albuquerque, L. Bodanese, L. Matsubara, R. M. Rocha, P. Genta, Z. Meneghelo, L. Oliveira, A. Lorga Filho, B. Garbelini, G. Oliveira, M. Teixeira, D. Precoma, E. Pelloso, A. Muniz, M. C. Braile, R. Ueda, A. R. Alves, P. Pimentel Filho, L. Zimerman, M. Coutinho, J. Silveira, H. Reis, D. Moreira, M. Paiva, J. L. Aziz, J. Gois, O. Dutra, L. Yao, G. Syan, B. Coutu, R. Chehayeb, G. Sabe-Affaki, C. Fortin, D. Borts, R. Bhargava, D. Fell, J. Cha, A. Pandey, P. Boucher, E. Sabbah, P. Ma, P. Talbot, D. Spence, A. Wade, M. Green, J. Berlingieri, S. Vizel, Y. K. Chan, M. Blostein, M. Talajic, L. Sterns, F. Grondin, T. Hruczkowski, R. Labonte, M. O'Mahony, D. Rupka, I. Mangat, A. Dowell, A. Kelly, F. St Maurice, S. Henein, K. Saunders, B. Lasko, M. Sami, R. MacKinnon, Q. Rizvi, D. O'Keefe, J. Ricci, B. Gervais, R. Hart, S. Bose, S. Nawaz, S. Connors, L. Winkler, M. Boileau, J. Healey, R. Collette, T. Rebane, B. Ramjattan, R. Senior, R. Therrien, P. Wells, C. Raffo, J. Cobos, S. Potthoff, B. Stockins, C. Pincetti, R. Corbalan, M. Vejar, S. Potthoff, W. Li, S. Zhao, X. Chen, S. Wu, H. Tan, S. Wu, P. Qu, X. Jiang, M. Wei, X. Yang, J. Li, S. Ma, S. Gu, Q. Y. Dai, L. Li, B. Yu, Y. Yin, N. Wang, L. Gao, S. X. Zhou, J. A. Wang, Z. Q. Li, F. Bai, F. Zhang, G. Lu, Y. Chen, Y. Zhang, D. Jiang, W. Zonggui, H. Li, K. Cao, Q. Lu, L. Li, T. Hu, H. Li, X. Wang, R. Botero, A. Reyes, N. Jaramillo, M. Urina, S. Velez, E. Gomez, L. Pava, D. Isaza, M. Dunaj, M. Hudcovic, O. Jerabek, R. Brat, J. Spinar, V. Dedek, E. Zidkova, I. Podpera, M. Cech, K. Gorican, M. Micko, M. Stribrna, L. Frost, C. Torp-Pedersen, C. T. Larsen, C. Tuxen, O. May, K. E. Pedersen, G. Jensen, T. Nielsen, O. Nyvad, S. Husted, M. G. Hansen, K. Egstrup, J. Lomholdt, K. Skagen, T. J. Jakobsen, M. Olsen, P. Grande, J. Melin, M. Tynni, V. P. Harjola, J. Strand, H. Parikka, T. inen, J. L. Corbelli, P. Gosse, A. Mirode, J. Mansourati, G. Lavabre, P. Defaye, P. G. Steg, G. Kahrman, T. Horacek, A. Bauer, S. Spitzer, M. Schlegl, B. Winkelmann, H. F. hringer, G. Stenzel, W. Haverkamp, J. Harenberg, M. Schumacher, J. Wunderlich, M. Natour, W. Rieker, S. Gass, J. Brachmann, J. Jung, H. Poppert, R. ge, L. Lickfett, R. Schoeller, L. Goedel-Meinen, A. Utech, M. Buerke, M. Maschke, R. Haberl, E. von Hodenberg, B. Griewing, F. Schlachetzki, H. Hamer, T. Hoch, M. Zabel, R. Jordan, F. gbauer, A. Hetzel, C. Weimar, P. Schauerte, D. Fischer, A. gge, A. Bittersohl, A. gge, K. Lee, C. Yu, F. Lakatos, A. rtes, A. cs, J. cs, A. s, J. Bakai, A. Papp, Á. s, J. nyi, I. I, Z. ó, A. Katona, L. gy, K. Keltai, C. zsi, G. Lupkovics, A. Cziraki, A. csi, K. Simon, S. Gupta, D. Agarwal, M. Fulwani, A. Naik, A. Nambiar, N. Chidambaram, B. Srinivasasastry, J. Joseph, M. Padinhare, P. Khanna, P. Grant, J. Arneja, M. Gadkari, N. Garg, R. B. Pothineni, S. Sathe, S. Ramesh, B. Malipeddi, A. Bharani, H. B. Gowdappa, V. S. Prakash, A. Dharmadhikari, S. Bhandari, N. Desai, S. Banerjee, N. Ghaisas, B. Ramagiri, S. Sinha, G. Gojanur, J. Duggal, V. Jain, S. Dani,

P. Singh, V. Srikanthan, V. K. Puri, R. Gopal, S. Viskin, M. Shochat, T. Hayek, L. Reisin, S. Rosenheck, B. Lewis, R. Zimlichman, A. Weiss, A. Marmor, Y. Turgeman, E. Klainman, A. Francis, M. Lahav, M. Omary, M. Morris, C. Olivieri, M. Santonastaso, R. Fenici, L. Mos, A. Ghirarduzzi, R. De Caterina, S. Novo, E. Richiardi, S. Testa, M. Pini, A. D'Angelo, A. Barsotti, M. Donati, M. Chiariello, M. Galli, G. Casolo, L. Moretti, Y. Atsushi, K. Yamamoto, S. Goto, H. Kihara, T. Akihiko, T. Saito, H. Yoshii, T. Sasaki, M. Suwa, S. Adachi, K. Usada, Y. Nakamura, K. Hayashida, T. Yamada, T. Iwasawa, Y. Kawase, K. Sugi, T. Murakami, K. Satake, T. Iwao, K. Maemura, Y. Koretsune, Y. Tsubokou, M. Yamashita, Y. Sato, F. Kouichi, S. Yura, A. Matsushima, K. Iwade, S. Kamakura, S. Tanaka, H. Murata, S. Yamamoto, Y. Kobayashi, Y. Higashi, T. Shinozaki, H. Ikeda, T. Hisaoka, K. Node, H. Takagi, T. K. Ong, I. Z. Abidin, Z. Yusof, K. Yusoff, O. Maskon, M. De los Rios Ibarra, M. Alcocer Gamba, E. Lopez Rosas, C. Calvo Vargas, P. Fajardo Campos, J. A. Cordero-Cabra, C. Jerjes-Sanchez, I. Hernandez Santamaria, L. Molina, R. Olvera Ruiz, C. Arean Martinez, J. Gonzalez Guerra, I. Morales Gonzalez, J. Cervantes-Escarcega, E. J. Chuquiure-Valenzuela, C. Riojas, J. Gonzalez Hermosillo, A. Galicia, P. Nierop, F. Verheugt, M. Daniels, D. Lok, A. Alings, M. Scholten, J. Plomp, R. Derksen, A. Bredero, P. Zwart, A. Schaap, H. Michels, C. Van der Zwaan, J. Hysing, S. Elle, T. Omland, P. nnevik, B. ie, J. E. Otterstad, N. Bogale, T. rnli, S. Halvorsen, B. Bryhni, K. Vikenes, W. Cabrera, A. Rodriguez, C. Chavez, R. Gamboa, L. Segura, O. Araoz, R. Azanero, L. Toce, F. Medina, G. Bustamante, C. Rios Vasquez, M. Zubiate, F. Collado, E. Morales-Palomares, R. Sy, D. Morales, G. Rogelio, M. T. Abola, E. Ramos, M. Yamamoto, F. Collado, F. De Leon, N. Abelardo, G. Kania, M. Szpajer, M. Rajzer, M. Janion, M. Bronisz, W. Ruzyllo, M. Piepiorka, M. Wendland, T. Czerski, R. Korzeniak, A. Budaj, L. Wawrzynska, M. Ogorek, P. Miekus, W. Tracz, A. Ocicka-Kozakiewicz, J. Stepinska, Z. Kiedrowicz, T. Pasierski, J. Kasprzak, M. Galewicz, B. Podogrodzka, M. Krauze-Wielicka, A. Chmielinski, A. Boruckowska-Kaszkowiak, W. Piotrowski, D. Vinereanu, S. Stamate, C. M. Cinteza, C. M. Tanaseanu, G. A. Dan, I. Benedek, R. M. Ionescu, D. Lighezan, A. Salajan, E. Carasca, R. Capalneau, C. Pop, C. G. Fierbinteanu-Braticevici, D. T. Zdrenghea, D. Gaita, I. Manitiu, T. Nanea, C. A. Georgescu, P. Chizhov, A. Kastanayan, V. Oleynikov, T. Treshkur, A. Govorin, T. Zhelninova, O. Barbarash, T. Novikova, O. Reshetko, E. Sivkova, A. Obrezan, E. Panchenko, S. Popov, A. Ivleva, D. Zotov, A. Gordienko, G. Kamalov, I. Chernichka, A. Levin, K. Zrazhevsky, S. Golitsyn, N. Shilkina, A. Golovach, G. Filonenko, S. Bondarev, V. Orlov, A. Bragina, N. Koziolova, A. Svistov, S. Shustov, I. Libov, O. Kisliak, E. Privalova, O. Aleksandrov, E. Mazur, Y. Karpov, D. Belenky, V. Kostenko, Y. Shubik, M. Ruda, G. Arutyunov, V. Eltishcheva, B. Sidorenko, R. Oseshnyuk, M. Boyarkin, Y. Pozdnyakov, N. Stakhinskiy, A. Sinopalnikov, S. Yakushin, A. Koniakhin, N. Yarohno, Z. Sizova, V. Zadionchenko, I. Klimov, D. Duplyakov, S. Kanorsky, V. Mareev, V. Terekhov, V. Arkhipov, T. Sotnikova, V. Yakusevich, V. Lesnov, I. Gordeev, N. Gratsiansky, S. Shalaev, V. Sulimov, O. Talibov, E. Zemtsovsky, O. Azarin, R. S. Tan, J. Thorne, D. De Jong, M. Basson, L. van Zyl, P. Commerford, H. Weich, E. van Nieuwenhuizen, J. Roos, D. Kelbe, J. Viljoen, T. J. Hong, B. H. Oh, K. S. Park, M. H. Jeong, C. Y. Rhim, D. J. Choi, J. H. Sung, Y. N. Kim, J. H. Bae, S. J. Tahk, K. H. Ryu, S. U. Kwon, T. H. Rho, T. J. Cha, D. G. Shin, P. a. M. Vida, E. Galve, J. Bruguera, J. Roquer, F. as de la Cruz, M. A. Paz Bermejo, T. Segura, J. H. mez, A. Ugarriza, I. rez, J. Villacastin, V. Bertomeu, R. Vargas, J. Serena Leal, J. Egidio Herrero, A. lez, X. Albert, C. Gonzalez Juanatey, V. Medrano, J. Vivancos, T. Andersson, C. J. Lindholm, F. Al-Khalili, C. glund, M. Rosenqvist, O. m, J. Herlitz, G. Rasmanis, L. Johansson, C. Christersson, O. Fredholm, F. Al-Khalili, M. Callander, H. Po, J. P. Pan, C. D. Tseng, K. G. Shyu, S. H. Chu, H. Kultursay, B. Gorenek, C. Erol, G. Lip, M. Albazzaz, H. Kadr, A. Cohen, J. Cooke, A. Agarwal, M. Brack, M. Pye, M. Anderson, F. Dunn, Y. K. Wong, S. Glen, G. Ford, A. Alwail, Z. Yousef, M. Blagden, D. Murdoch, G. McInnes, J. Camm, W. R. Smith, J. J. McMurray, R. Senior, J. Webster, D. Dutka, B. McClements, Z. Yousef, T. Levy, S. Yogasundram, A. Moriarty, M. McCullagh, J. Flather, M. Gumbley, I. Findlay, J. Davies, A. Cooke, A. Ahsan, J. Cannon, A. Bakhai, A. Jacob, T. Trouton, A. Ajala, A. Bartkowiak, D. Humiston, W. Kufs, K. Klancke, P. Jetty, D. Gupta, V. Nadar, K. Yousuf, G. Sosa-Suarez, S. Gill, M. Wukelic, N. Mayer, D. Colan, E. Haskel, P. Grena, V. Haight, R. Walsh, K. Carr, N. Tahirkheli, M. Jardula, J. Cebe, S. Bloom, S. Bilazarian, R. Gilmore, N. Jaffrani, D. Goldscher, A. Lebowitz, I. Friedlander, M. Stein, S. Promisloff, A. Magnano, J. Dean, J. Gerber, D. Perloff, Y. Cohen, A. Meholick, T. Tobin, R. Acheatel, P. Levanovich, J. Ip, J. Porterfield, N. Seshadri, M. McKenzie, A. Alfieri, R. Gazmuri, B. Beanblossom, D. Van Hamersveld, J. McCriskin, M. Gelernt, W. Bowden, C. Sotolongo, J. Lang, S. Kaatz, F. Agnone, D. Hassman, E. Flores, F. Albrecht, C. Hassel, J. Quartner, J. LaFata, N. Bedwell, W. Herzog, J. Amin, J. Usedom, A. Brockmyre, R. Abadier, C. Corder, R. Marple, C. Lovell, W. Henry, A. Chhabra, S. Baker, R. Bedoya, R. Sandoval, M. Nathan, D. Garcia, K. Vora, S. Sloan, E. Kosinski, R. Foster, A. Salacata, R. Weachter, C. Bredlau, P. Mehta, C. Russo, R. Swint, S. Rosenthal, K. Bybee, B. Peart, P. Chaudhuri, B. Iteld, M. Staab, D. Rhodes, J. Kappler, M. Mandviwala, O. Niedermaier, C. Sofley, M. Heiman, S. Gips, R. Harris, C. East, V. Nguyen, R. Huling, U. Thadani, D. Travis, F. Maislos, M. West, R. Castello, K. Cohen, R. Karlsberg, J. Schmedtje, D. Gottlieb, A. MacKinnon, G. Noble, P. O'Neill, J. Roth, J. Kobayashi, M. Honan, G. Hanovich, S. Ehrlich, W. Wilson, A. Warner, A. Rubin, E. Rivera, S. Leu, L. Smith, J. Agaiby, M. Jan, R. Gould, S. Weiner, J. Fleming, J. Hemphill, K. Parr, M. Stoddard, P. Curran, K. Kurrelmeyer, V. Desai, D. Kereiakes, E. Schwarz, M. Lillestol, J. Vazquez-Tanus, R. Vicari, J. White, R. Shroff, R. Fierer, N. Vijay, A. Hamad, M. Kozinn, D. Young, S. Fenton, P. Ouyang, A. Wellford, P. Zwerner, P. Meyer, J. Foley, A. Boyle, M. Dotani, A. Skolnick, C. Rodriguez-Fierro, B. Hattler, M. Rubin, P. Hartley, L. Tami, E. Ball, C. McPherson, S. Eisenberg, I. Niazi, M. Orlov, B. Bachhuber, C. Massey, W. Phillips, E. Mouhayar, J. Griffin, E. Blumberg, S. Slabic, K. Danisa, A. Samal, S. Rohrbeck, P. McCullough, D. Dohan, G. Aycock, A. Jones, J. Anderson, R. Silverman, W. Smith, D. Mishkel, N. Patterson, H. Moore, A. Kabour, M. Muttreja, W. Jaffrani, T. Vidic, S. Kent, B. Platt, R. Goldberg, S. Kulback, R. Patel, A. Bazzi, S. Goldman, A. Roman, C. Levin, B. Lachterman, Y. Chandrashekhar, I. Aisiku, C. Powers, E. Engeron, R. Bernstein, S. Shah, J. Strobel, H. Punatar, R. Garcia, D. Linden, A. Al-Mudamgha, A. Quick, J. Kramer, G. Feldman, D. Stapleton, M. Davis, J. Graff, J. Galizia, P. Wassmer, D. Chiu, R. Ison, K. Curry, M. Finneran, A. Solomon, B. Schifferdecker, J. Seger, A. Alexander, S. Yates, R. Ashley, J. Cordero-Sepulveda, P. Cowen, T. Ayres, B. Kowalski, S. Anton, J. Phillips, D. Donovan, A. Patel, R. Smith, J. Updegrove, A. Buxton, D. Clark, J. Margolis, G. Brooks, R. Pernenkil, J. Walters, M. Richards,

P. Maccaro, M. Pieniek, J. G. Pulido, C. W. Lee, J. Ilvento, D. Riff, B. Blue, J. Welker, H. Karunaratne, P. Santucci, M. Vatutin, I. Kraiz, Y. Mostovoy, O. Karpenko, V. Tseluyko, L. Kononenko, V. Volkov, A. Parkhomenko, G. Popik, I. Chohey, Y. Burmak, S. Pavlyk, V. Vizir, O. Barna, O. Sychov, I. Vykhovanyuk, V. Tashchuk, I. Khomazjuk, S. Andrievskaya, Z. Telyatnikova, O. Bondarchuk, V. Netiazhenko, N. Seredyuk, O. Koval, I. Kovalsky, A. Bazylevych, G. Lysenko, M. Borschivsky, A. Yagensky, G. Dzyak, I. Bereznyakov, L. Rudenko, G. Ignatenko, K. Amosova, O. Voloshyna, L. Ivanova, S. Tykhonova, and E. Suprun. Apixaban versus warfarin in patients with atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med*, 365(11):981–992, Sep 2011. [PubMed](#) .

John Burdon Sanderson Haldane. The fitting of binomial distributions. *Annals of Eugenics*, 11(1):179–181, 1941. ISSN 2050-1439. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-1809.1941.tb02283.x. [Wiley Online Library](#) .

Friedrich Robert Helmert. Über die Wahrscheinlichkeit der Potenzsummen der Beobachtungsfehler und über einige damit im Zusammenhang stehende Fragen. *Zeitschrift für Mathematik und Physik*, 21(3):102–219, 1876.

Christiaan Huygens and Frans van Schooten. *De ratiociniis in ludo alae: In: Exercitationum mathematicarum liber primus [- quintus].* ex officina Johannis Elsevirii, Lugdunum Batavorum (Leiden, The Netherlands), January 1657. doi: 10.3931/e-rara-8813. Free full text: [e-rara, Zurich, CH](#) .

B. M. Kissela, J. C. Khoury, K. Alwell, C. J. Moomaw, D. Woo, O. Adeoye, M. L. Flaherty, P. Khatri, S. Ferioli, F. De Los Rios La Rosa, J. P. Broderick, and D. O. Kleindorfer. Age at stroke: temporal trends in stroke incidence in a large, biracial population. *Neurology*, 79(17):1781–1787, Oct 2012. [PubMed](#) .

B. Ovbiagele and M. N. Nguyen-Huynh. Stroke epidemiology: advancing our understanding of disease mechanism and therapy. *Neurotherapeutics*, 8(3):319–329, Jul 2011. [PubMed](#) .

J. S. Paikin, M. J. Haroun, and J. W. Eikelboom. Dabigatran for stroke prevention in atrial fibrillation: the RE-LY trial. *Expert Rev Cardiovasc Ther*, 9(3):279–286, Mar 2011. [PubMed](#) .

M. R. Patel, K. W. Mahaffey, J. Garg, G. Pan, D. E. Singer, W. Hacke, G. Breithardt, J. L. Halperin, G. J. Hankey, J. P. Piccini, R. C. Becker, C. C. Nessel, J. F. Paolini, S. D. Berkowitz, K. A. Fox, R. M. Califf, R. C. Becker, J. Paolini, G. Breithardt, W. Hacke, J. L. Halperin, G. J. Hankey, K. W. Mahaffey, C. C. Nessel, D. E. Singer, R. M. Califf, K. A. Fox, D. Ardissino, A. Avezum, P. Aylward, B. Biedermann, G. Breithardt, C. Bode, A. Carolei, R. n, L. Csiba, A. Dalby, R. Diaz, H. C. Diener, G. Donnan, S. Goodman, H. chel, D. Y. Hu, K. Huber, G. Jensen, M. Keltai, B. Lewis, J. n, G. MacInnes, J. L. Mas, A. Massaro, B. Norrving, M. Penicka, D. Prabhakaran, R. Roine, P. A. Sirnes, V. Skvortsova, P. G. Steg, R. S. Tan, H. White, L. Wong, J. Alpert, G. Boysen, J. Eikelboom, P. Rothwell, A. Skene, K. Hannan, K. Schwabe, S. Mohanty, L. Oppenheimer, Z. Zhang, G. Pan, J. Garg, S. K. Sapp, J. Anderson, N. Bedwell, M. Bilsker, G. Bruce, R. Agah, M. DeSantis, S. Eisenberg, A. Flores, W. Herzog, S. Klein, H. Snyder, S. Krueger, E. Almaguer, E. Lavie, C. Lee, G. Mallis, M. Modi, G. Woodworth, I. Niazi, B. Peart, S. Sundaram, B. Snoddy, R. Sotolongo, J. Moloney, K. Vijayaraghavan, F. Whittier, L. Yellen, S. Banerjee, D. Lustgarten, D. Suresh, M. Gelernt, L. Levinson, R. Ghanekar, I. Niazi, G. Kneller, C. Hall, Y. Fadl, D. Suresh, M. Pirwitz, W. French, N. Mayer, J. Pugada, K. Steel, F. Mody, A. Malik, H. Chandna, A. Go, G. Emlein, W. Bowden, R. Moscoto, R. Hodson, M. Berk, D. Pan, J. Pappas, R. Orchard, G. Lynchard, N. Vijay, W. Khan, M. El Khadra, M. Antonishen, F. Cucher, M. Staab, J. Zembrack, S. Borromeo, J. Heilman, S. Chaturvedi, S. Makam, S. Turk, T. Hyers, G. Williams, A. Labroo, S. Gill, D. Myears, J. Weinstein, J. Shanes, Y. Chandrashekar, S. Shah, W. Reiter, T. Logemann, A. Almquist, R. Bhagwat, T. Tak, J. Shen-Ling, P. Patel, A. Artis, A. Arouni, M. Lauer, K. Kinney, J. Elsen, P. Roan, R. Villafria, M. Sumpter, J. Ip, S. Welka, B. Schifferdecker, R. Sandoval, S. Speirs, A. Jones, T. Haldis, J. Kazmierski, J. Sutherland, D. Dietrich, E. Telfer, J. Berry, A. McElveen, J. Russell, M. Sackett, N. Antonios, D. Smith, K. Vora, A. Kirby, H. Lui, D. Mego, K. Ziada, J. Navas, A. Taussig, M. Koren, C. Vogel, F. Saba, C. Parrott, R. Schneider, A. Shirwany, M. Rubin, C. Treasure, B. Bertolet, M. Chang, J. Langberg, R. Becker, Y. Cohen, F. McGrew, J. White, F. Arzola, J. Zelenka, A. Tannenbaum, V. Fernandes, P. Jannadas, J. Agamasu, B. Collins, W. Jauch, B. Sasseen, D. Hotchkiss, R. Abadier, A. Osunkoya, A. Schlaue, C. Chappel, M. Foster, E. Braun, E. Mostel, J. Capo, M. Ashchi, V. Howard, A. Albirini, A. Burger, D. Rolston, C. Staniloae, J. Bacon, A. Wiseman, J. McGarvey, A. Sonel, G. Hamroff, D. Chang, N. Daboul, G. Broderick, A. Meholic, J. Corbelli, R. Silverman, J. Raffetto, R. Fishberg, S. Georgeson, J. Held, M. Seidner, H. Saint-Jacques, J. Heitner, S. Kutalek, I. Friedlander, B. Hutchinson, J. Walia, N. Kondo, N. Smiley, L. Blitz, H. Dale, S. Sulman, I. Szulawski, F. Modares, R. Martin, A. Nahhas, M. Renzi, A. Akyea-Djamson, A. Alfieri, J. Sandhu, S. Voyce, S. Amaram, G. Meyerrose, M. Shoukfeh, F. Lee, B. Villegas, O. Idowu, A. Khera, C. Sam, A. Vo, I. Lieber, T. Smith, N. Awan, C. Tsai, R. Ganim, G. Alzaghri, W. Pitt, A. Shepherd, S. Tang, A. Go, S. Stoltz, W. Nelson, S. Cox, S. Meymandi, M. Melucci, G. Thomas, H. Gogia, C. Machell, S. Chandrasekaran, C. Brown, P. Jetty, G. Miller, G. Dykstra, N. Jaffrani, B. Zakhary, A. Caruso, R. Zolty, D. Fox, G. Jacobs, M. Leberthal, S. Mukherjee, P. Zimetbaum, J. Kingsley, R. Jones, V. Robinson, D. Kenton, J. Usedom, S. Williams, C. Snipes, V. Wilson, R. Hasty, J. Shoemaker, V. Robinson, M. Donahue, Y. Al-Saghir, E. Thomsen, S. Yarows, S. Chastain, P. McLaughlin, M. Wakham, D. Shrestha, J. Simmons, D. Fisher, Z. Seymour, B. Frandsen, B. First, C. Sharpe, L. Popeil, R. Guthrie, J. Hunter, O. Alvarado, J. Sandberg, N. Gutman, A. Belber, M. Arkhipov, M. Ballyzek, A. Baranov, O. Barbarash, V. Barbarich, D. Belenky, O. Berkovich, I. Bokarev, M. Boyarkin, S. Vaniev, E. Volkova, N. Gratsiansky, A. Demin, V. Zadiionchenko, D. Zateyshchikov, K. Zrazhevsky, V. Mazaev, A. Martynov, S. Mikhailov, V. Mkrchtian, V. Novozhenov, T. Raskina, A. Rebrov, N. Sanina, V. Simanekov, M. Sitnikova, O. Smolenskaya, R. Stryuk, G. Storozhakov, B. Tankhilevich, S. Tereschenko, A. Khokhlov, O. Khrustalev, S. Chernov, Y. Shvarts, Y. Shubik, V. Shulman, S. Yakushin, O. Bugrova, A. Ivleva,

R. Libis, N. Khozyainova, S. Maslov, E. Baranova, A. Sherenkov, I. Libov, V. Lusov, G. Chumakova, V. Kuznetsov, I. Ryamzina, O. Reshetko, S. Boldueva, N. Alekseeva, T. Novikova, V. Dvornikov, E. Idrisova, N. Shostak, N. Yarokhno, K. Tebloev, T. Treshkur, V. Mazurov, E. Loktin, I. Sedavnyh, O. Alexeeva, P. Yakhontova, A. Repin, N. Izmozherova, V. Kostenko, A. Fokin, G. Ketova, S. Kouz, R. Leader, F. Ayala-Paredes, R. Luton, P. Ma, S. Pandey, Y. Pesant, R. Senior, G. Vertes, A. Bell, D. Crowley, S. Vizel, B. Lasko, D. Landry, L. Berger, J. Heath, R. Bessoudo, M. Ling, G. Tellier, J. Berlingieri, H. Kafka, L. Hill, G. Mazza, W. O'Mahony, M. Chilvers, M. O'Mahony, D. Newman, D. Newman, D. Newman, S. Silagy, M. Heffernan, M. Bennett, T. Bhesania, G. Rockman, K. Ng, B. Kalra, G. Meneses, W. Liang, M. Cheung, J. Kozak, G. Pugen, J. Vavougiou, M. Kates, C. Nunes-Vaz, S. Jaffer, J. Orfi, A. Faiers, C. Chung, S. Felsen, S. Bergman, I. Bernstein, L. Brownscombe, J. Stockdill, E. Silver, D. Ezekiel, N. Jagan, M. Khurana, H. Reisler, H. Goldman, T. Maung, F. Wong, G. Gillis, R. Vexler, B. Goldberg, M. Luteran, D. Gould, B. Coutu, A. Ouellet, P. MacDonald, M. Jones, R. Collette, P. Chong, T. Fargher, F. St-Maurice, C. Fortin, R. Chehayeb, G. Proulx, R. Roy, J. Liutkus, G. Syan, D. Rupka, T. Lichtenstein, J. Kooy, D. Papastergiou, B. Lubelsky, W. Doyle, A. Rajakumar, J. Cha, A. Choudhry, H. Bhamjee, A. Mawji, M. Durfresne, C. Constance, J. Mutrie, A. Najarali, R. Warren, M. Mucha, D. Borts, P. Nord, S. Carrier, M. Dawood, G. Sabe-Affaki, J. Archibald, N. Abram, E. Teitelbaum, I. Ebrahim, R. Siebert, L. van Zyl, H. Theron, E. Lloyd, R. Sommers, G. Podgorski, L. Steingo, A. Dalby, J. Bayat, L. Herbst, F. Bester, C. Corbett, J. Bennett, A. Roodt, J. Roux, M. Abelsson, Z. Mohamed, H. Nortje, A. Da Silva, K. Nikolaidis, K. Liagkas, E. Papasteriadis, A. Achimastos, N. Koliopoulos, A. Trikas, A. Manolis, J. Ruitter, D. Basart, H. Crijns, A. Withagen, M. Janssen, R. Van Langeveld, I. van Gelder, B. Hamer, R. Van der Heijden, D. Hertzberger, M. Van Hessen, M. Pieterse, R. Groutars, A. Kuijper, G. De Ruitter, A. van Boven, P. Hoogslag, H. Kragten, H. Thijssen, R. Veldkamp, C. Scavee, H. Heidbuchel, P. Debruyne, B. Deruyter, H. El Ali, M. Goethals, R. Cytryn, H. Strickwold, L. De Wolf, P. Goethals, F. Provénier, S. Hellemans, M. Galinier, D. Coisne, A. Koenig, D. Galley, L. Destrac, J. Leduc, A. Rifai, B. Citron, E. Ellie, P. Fournier, G. Steg, R. Landel, A. Robinson, F. Ziegler, J. Boulliat, M. Zuber, M. Vida, E. Galve Basilio, M. Lopez, C. Iiguez, L. Iglesias Alonso, M. Caverio Gibanel, J. Olivan Martinez, F. Calvo Iglesias, P. Marco Vera, J. Bruguera Cortada, A. Jaber Houbani, J. Merino, F. Olaz Preciado, J. Balaguer, J. de la Hera Galarza, A. Martinez Rubio, J. Fontcuberta, J. Sotillo Marti, J. Gonzalez Juanatey, R. Del Campo, G. Vivanco, P. Alvarez Garcia, M. Pelayo, J. Lippai, K. Zamolyi, T. roly, A. Vertes, A. Nagy, I. Kosa, A. Janosi, G. Lupkovics, E. Kalo, T. Forster, E. Kis, J. Tenczer, D. Bereczki, S. Komoly, A. Csanyi, R. Kiss, A. Valikovics, P. Dioszeghy, F. Masini, P. Terrosu, V. Cirrincione, C. Marabotti, F. Cosmi, A. Salvioni, G. Binetti, G. Piovaccari, D. Nassiacos, G. Boriani, V. Calvi, R. De Caterina, V. Pengo, G. Parati, A. Carolei, A. D'Angelo, M. Di Biase, L. Fattore, G. Agnelli, P. Merlini, M. Furlan, M. Rasura, C. Gandolfo, W. Ageno, F. Piovella, G. Micieli, M. Cinteza, C. Fierbinteanu, D. Natase-Melicovic, D. Ionescu, C. Macarie, I. Nanea, M. Radoi, G. Tatu-Chitoiu, S. Dragulescu, A. Tudose, C. Militaru, C. Bengus, G. Ungureanu, A. Tau, V. Popa, O. Pirvu, M. Bojinca, D. Sipciu, M. Popescu, M. Chiru, D. Vinereanu, M. Tudoran, T. Cojocar, M. Vintila, G. Aron, O. Petrascu, F. Bolohan, R. Baumgartner, L. Sekoranja, J. Vojacek, B. Lacnak, I. Kellnerova, M. Dunaj, C. Cihalik, T. Janota, J. Janousek, P. Bouchal, R. Spacek, J. Choi Siruckova, P. Heinc, P. Vojtisek, M. Pirchala, J. Malecha, F. Padour, A. Linhart, E. Mandysova, J. Jandik, E. Zidkova, D. Sipula, P. Ostadal, R. Polasek, V. Stransky, G. Marcinek, D. Rysava, P. Osmancik, K. Huber, H. Drexel, M. Brainin, S. Eichinger-Hasenauer, W. Lang, E. Pilger, A. Moriarty, I. Hudson, K. Tang, J. Cleland, R. MacWalter, J. Cooke, G. McInnes, R. Durairaj, M. MacLeod, D. Murdoch, H. Kadr, G. Lip, R. Andrews, B. Hunt, P. Jackson, M. MacLeod, C. Roffe, H. Syed, P. Bath, J. Coyle, D. Kelly, S. Stender, C. Torp-Pedersen, C. Tuxen, G. Jensen, T. Melchior, K. Klarlund, C. Dahlstrom, T. Nielsen, E. Nielsen, J. Bronnum-Schou, R. Sykalski, P. Blomstrom, C. Lindholm, T. Wallen, C. Nilsson, E. Bertholds, J. Carl-sater, P. Sirnes, S. Elle, K. Risberg, K. Furuseth, A. Skag, H. Hovik, N. Landmark, T. Kjaernli, J. Berg-Johansen, G. Gradek, A. Drzewiecki, W. Pluta, H. Szwed, M. Trusz-Gluza, M. Ogorek, K. Lobo-Grudzien, P. Ruskowski, R. Sciborski, J. Kopaczewski, K. Jaworska, J. Kubica, G. Opolski, A. Hoffman, M. Krzyciuk, W. Sinkiewicz, W. Piotrowski, P. Kolodziej, M. Goszczynska, A. Rynkiewicz, L. Chojnowska, J. Lewczuk, M. Biedrzycka, M. Piepiorka, J. Kowal, A. Karczmarczyk, P. Pruszczyk, M. Tendera, Z. Gaciong, M. Krzeminska-Pakula, Z. Kornacewicz-Jach, G. Kania, J. Brachmann, H. Lawall, H. Guelker, S. Spitzer, S. Moebius-Winkler, C. Dempfle, C. Bode, H. Darius, S. Genth-Zotz, S. Sommer, J. Roehnisch, R. Strasser, W. Daenschel, C. Schwencke, J. vom Dahl, M. Meuser, S. Behrens-Spandau, S. Behrens-Humboldt, A. Muegge, N. Schoen, P. Grooterhorst, H. Ebert, A. Kraemer, B. Kohler, J. Taggeselle, G. Claus, H. Sarnighausen, A. Al-Zoebi, T. Schroeder, M. Weissbrodt, R. Lange, M. Gabelmann, S. Kaeab, M. Doerr, D. Boscher, R. Bosch, F. Sonntag, C. Bauknecht, H. Omran, M. Leicht, R. Veltkamp, H. Hohensee, H. Dieckmann, B. Winkelmann, P. Bernhardt, A. Schnabel, C. Kadel, N. Proskynitopoulos, K. Seidl, S. Schellong, C. Rios, C. Guevara, R. Coloma, H. Torrejon, J. Parra Galvan, J. Drago Silva, J. Gallegos, A. Mendoza, S. Negron, L. Watanabe, F. Medina, L. Virgen Carrilo, H. Alvarez Lopez, I. Rodriguez, J. Leiva-Pons, A. os Velasco, J. Villarreal-Careaga, M. De los Rios, M. Alcocer Gamba, G. Llamas Esperon, E. Villeda, A. Ahuad Guerrero, A. Alvariqueta, M. Amuchastegui, J. Bluguermann, G. Caime, C. Cuneo, A. Gabito, D. Garcia Brasca, M. Hominal, H. Jure, H. Luquez, O. Montana, D. Piskorz, S. Listorti, J. Serra, H. Sessa, S. Varini, N. Vita, J. Aiub, I. MacKinnon, S. Chekherdemian, J. Castagnino, J. Cimbaro Canella, H. Sgammini, A. Escudero, G. Albina, C. Rapallo, C. Balparda, M. Chahin, V. Fuentealba, M. Riccitelli, J. Casabe, L. Lobo Marquez, R. Kevorkian, J. Cuadrado, R. Dran, J. Muntaner, M. Gonzalez, L. Cartasegna, E. Hasbani, A. Hrabar, A. Sanchez, D. Vogel, A. Hershson, A. Avezum, J. Jaber, P. E. Leaes, A. Bozza, A. Lorga Filho, P. Pimentel Filho, J. M. Jorge, L. Maia, E. Manenti, R. D. Mora, J. de Souza Neto, D. Precoma, A. Rabelo, J. Rocha, P. Rossi, J. K. Saraiva, L. Zimerman, L. Bodanese, E. Figueiredo, W. S. de Souza, J. Braga, S. Alessi, M. Gomes, R. Silva, M. Teixeira, F. Costa, M. Motta, D. Sobral Filho, G. Reis, B. Garbelini, S. Zimmermann, A. Pereira Barretto, H. Dohmann, J. Barreto Filho, N. Ghorayeb, F. Borelli, F. R. dos Santos, M. L. Prudente, M. Vejar, F. Lanas, R. Del Pino, S. Potthoff, G. Charne, A. Aguirre, A. Saldana, E. Garces, L. Bunster, H. Figueroa, C. Olivares, C. Raffo, E. Vergara, P. Sepulveda, G. Jano, J. Morales Alvarado, R. Suarez, M. Urina, G. Perez, A. Quintero, L. Pava, R. Botero Lopez, C. Luengas, E. Hernandez, D. Sanchez, C. Poveda, J. Coronel, R. Bel-

tran, C. Jaramillo, J. Pardo, C. Ponte Negretti, J. Isea, G. Vergara, I. Morr, K. Sim, W. W. Ahmad, Z. Yusof, A. Rosman, H. Basri, P. Thompson, I. Jeffery, P. Purnell, P. Roberts-Thomson, W. Heddle, J. Waites, D. Walters, J. Amerena, P. Challa, J. Karrasch, A. Lowy, D. Fitzpatrick, M. Parsons, T. Phan, J. Karrasch, J. Karrasch, C. Bladin, G. Donnan, G. Aroney, R. Gerraty, C. Anderson, P. Blombery, P. Martin, K. T. Wijeratne, D. Cross, D. Crimmins, D. Packham, D. Jackson, W. Chua, R. Merino, M. Magno, L. Tirador, E. Batalla, C. Manalo, N. Uy, G. Ebo, E. Reyes, A. Bernan, M. Richards, H. Hart, S. Mann, R. Fisher, R. Stewart, G. Wilkins, A. Barber, R. Tan, H. Ong, R. Singh, A. Sukonthasarn, S. Tanomsup, R. Krittayaphong, C. Piamsomboon, D. Piyayotai, B. Sunsaneewitayakul, S. Baek, H. Seo, S. Rim, C. Kim, K. Kim, K. Ryu, S. Jo, S. Tahk, H. Lee, C. Kim, Y. Kim, D. Shin, Y. Choi, N. Chung, J. Namgung, C. Kim, T. Hong, W. Shin, S. Jin, X. Yan, G. Fu, G. Lu, K. Yang, D. Xu, J. Chen, J. Liu, S. Wu, J. Song, Y. Liao, B. Xu, Z. Li, S. Ma, Y. Yin, Y. Zhao, D. Hu, C. Ma, J. Ma, J. Sun, H. Li, X. Hong, B. Yu, Q. Lu, J. Yang, Z. Wu, Y. Li, Y. Huang, Y. Wang, M. Liu, Y. Cheng, T. Yang, K. Chen, H. Wang, Z. Yuan, J. Wang, Z. Zeng, Y. Chen, O. Yavuzgil, O. Kozan, M. Etemoglu, E. Diker, A. Belgi, C. Ceyhan, V. Cin, O. Yilmaz, N. Ata, B. Altunkeser, A. A. Agir, A. Karadede, R. Topsakal, R. Gulati, A. Madhavan, S. Jain, A. Oomman, S. Janorkar, P. Kumar, A. M. Naik, H. Thacker, V. Rajasekhar, R. Reddy, C. Keshavamurthy, P. Jain, B. Gowdappa, M. Gadkari, A. Abhyankar, B. R. Babu, P. Vydiathan, S. Sinha, N. Garg, S. Rao, P. Gautam, K. Chockalingam, M. Kumbla, R. Panwar, D. Banker, M. Kaste, P. ä, R. Roine, A. Mihov, D. Raev, V. Yordanova, S. Dimitrova, H. Benov, V. Tsanova, M. Kyolean, S. Marchev, A. Stoikov, N. Zdravkov, K. Ramshev, A. Krastev, P. Stamenova, I. Angelova, G. Pencheva, V. Grigorova, B. Petrauskiene, I. Skripkauskiene, R. Raugaliene, S. Norkiene, R. Mazutavicius, A. Kavoliuniene, S. Aidietiene, J. Aganauskiene, A. Dailydkiene, J. Marcinkeviciene, L. Grigoniene, J. Anusauskiene, R. Kavaliauskiene, V. Lizogub, L. Rudenko, V. Tseluyko, L. Voronkov, O. Sychov, Y. Svyshchenko, Y. Sirenko, V. Serkova, N. Seredyuk, T. Pertseva, V. Netyazhenko, V. Lishnevskaya, O. Kupchynska, O. Koval, G. Koshukova, O. Karpenko, O. Grishyna, A. Faynyk, G. Dzyak, O. Dyadyk, L. Yena, V. Volkov, I. Rudyk, M. Kopytsya, L. Kononenko, K. Amosova, S. Zhurba, V. Kazimirko, I. Iuzkiv, O. Shershnyova, T. Khomazyuk, V. Batushkin, I. Vykhovanyuk, G. Popik, V. Skrebkov, A. Skurtov, T. Mishchenko, N. Lytvynenko, L. Sokolova, M. Vatutin, M. Shved, B. Rebrov, L. Kadina, M. Vajda, G. Ursol, V. Zheleznyy, T. Vysochanska, A. Gozhenko, K. Fan, D. Ho, H. Tse, C. Yu, L. Wong, H. Yeh, P. Pai, I. Hsieh, C. Huang, Y. Hsieh, W. Yin, L. Tsai, T. Huang, C. Chen, F. Chiang, K. Ueng, M. Charng, H. Yeh, A. Marmor, A. Katz, A. Butnaru, B. Lewis, M. Eldar, S. Rosenhack, N. Elias, B. Koifman, M. Shochat, M. Swissa, R. Zimlichman, T. Bental, A. Weiss, R. Ganam, M. Elias, W. Nseir, A. Oliven, B. Brenner, and M. Dayan. Rivaroxaban versus warfarin in nonvalvular atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med*, 365(10):883–891, Sep 2011. [PubMed](#) .

Karl Pearson. X. Contributions to the mathematical theory of evolution. — II. Skew variation in homogeneous material. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. (A.)*, 186:343–414, Jan 1895. doi: 10.1098/rsta.1895.0010. [Publisher: Royal Society](#) .

Karl Pearson. XV. On certain properties of the hypergeometrical series, and on the fitting of such series to observation polygons in the theory of chance. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 47(285):236–246, January 1899. ISSN 1941-5982. doi: 10.1080/14786449908621253. [Taylor and Francis](#) .

Karl Pearson. X. On the Criterion that a Given System of Deviations from the Probable in the Case of a Correlated System of Variables is such that it can be Reasonably Supposed to have Arisen from Random Sampling. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 50(302):157–175, 1900.

Karl Pearson. III. Mathematical contributions to the theory of evolution. — XII. On a generalised Theory of alternative Inheritance, with special reference to Mendel's laws. *p 66: Standard dev binomial distribution*, 203(359–371):53–86, 1 1904a. doi: 10.1098/rsta.1904.0015. [Royal Society](#) .

Karl Pearson. *Mathematical contributions to the theory of evolution. XIII. On the theory of contingency and its relation to association and normal correlation*. Biometric Series I. Dulau and Co., London, January 1904b. Free full text: [archive.org](#), [San Francisco, CA 94118, USA](#) .

Karl Pearson. *The Grammar of Science. Third Edition*. Adam and Charles Black, London (GB), 1911. ISBN 978-1-108-07711-8. doi: 10.1017/CBO9781139878548. Free full text: [archive.org](#), [San Francisco, CA 94118, USA](#) .

Dror M Rom. A sequentially rejective test procedure based on a modified bonferroni inequality. *Biometrika*, 77(3):663–665, 1990.

M. Saini, K. Ikram, S. Hilal, A. Qiu, N. Venketasubramanian, and C. Chen. Silent stroke: not listened to rather than silent. *Stroke*, 43(11):3102–3104, Nov 2012. [PubMed](#) .

John Wilder Tukey. *Multiple comparisons: 1948-1983*. In: The collected works of John W. Tukey. Volume VIII. Ed. by Henry I. Braun, with the assistance of Bruce Kaplan, Kathleen M. Sheehan, Min-Hwei Wang. New York, Chapman and Hall, 1994. ISBN 0-412-05121-4.

J. v. Uspensky. *Introduction To Mathematical Probability*. McGraw-Hill Company, New York (USA), 1937. [Archive.org](#) .

Frank Yates. Contingency Tables Involving Small Numbers and the Chi square Test. *Supplement to the Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 1(2):217–235, 1934. ISSN 1466-6162. doi: 10.2307/2983604. [JSTOR](#) .

Associated Data**Copyright**

Copyright © August 6, 2023 by Ilija Barukčić, Horandstrasse, Jever, Germany. All Rights Reserved. Alle Rechte vorbehalten.

© 2024 Ilija Barukčić^{a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m} Ilija Barukčić, Chief-Editor, Jever, Germany, August 6, 2023. All rights reserved. Alle Rechte vorbehalten. This is an open access article which can be downloaded under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).

I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

^a<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6988-2780>

^b<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/1972920>

^c<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=37099674500>

^d<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=54974181600>

^e<https://www.mendeley.com/search/?authorFullName=Ilija%20Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87&page=1&query=Barukcic&sortBy=relevance>

^f<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ilija-Barukcic-2>

^g<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87%22&sort=mostviewed>

^h<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87,%20Conference%22>

ⁱ<https://twitter.com/ilijabarukcic?lang=de>

^jhttps://twitter.com/Causation_Journ

^khttps://vixra.org/author/ilija_barukcic

^l<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwf3w1IngcukI00jpw8HTwg>

^m<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any¤tPosition=30>